

Master Thesis

Detection of Prebiosignature
Molecules in Temperate Exoplanetary
Atmospheres with LIFE

Jacopo Bottoni
jbottoni@student.ethz.ch

Supervisor
Prof. Dr. Sascha P. Quanz

October 6, 2025

Institute of Particle Physics and Astrophysics
Department of Physics
ETH Zürich

Abstract

Context – The Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE) is a proposed space mission concept designed to directly detect and characterize temperate, terrestrial exoplanets in the mid-infrared (MIR). A key preparatory step is to quantify how reliably atmospheric retrievals can recover prebiosignature molecules from simulated observations.

Aims – We investigate the detectability and retrieval performance of potential pre-biosignatures (HCN, H₂S, NO, CH₄, C₂H₂, SO₂) and key background gases (H₂O, CO, CO₂, H₂, N₂) in early Earth analog atmospheres. We examine how these results depend on water content (dry vs. non-dry models) and assess the importance of the 4–6 μm spectral range that includes the 4.7 μm CO band.

Methods – We generated synthetic MIR emission spectra between 4–18.5 μm at a spectral resolution of $R = 100$ for five atmospheric scenarios representative of early Earth conditions. Wavelength-dependent photon noise was added using the LIFEsim simulator, and Bayesian retrievals were performed at three global signal-to-noise levels ($S/N = 10, 20, 50$ at 11.2 μm). Retrieval performance was assessed using Bayes factors, posterior classifications, and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) between the retrieved and true spectra to quantify overall accuracy.

Results – The retrieved fluxes reproduce the input spectra within the simulated noise, confirming the robustness of the retrieval framework. Surface temperature, pressure, and planetary radius are well constrained, while the planetary mass remains partially degenerate with composition. Water vapor strongly influences retrieval outcomes: in non-dry cases, the upper-atmosphere H₂O is systematically underestimated, biasing mass and abundance estimates, whereas dry models improve surface constraints. CO₂, CH₄, and SO₂ are robustly detected across scenarios, while H₂S, HCN, and C₂H₂ are often retrieved as upper limits. CO, NO, H₂, and N₂ remain unconstrained under the considered conditions. Excluding the 4–6 μm region has little effect on retrieval performance, as CO is not reliably detected through its 4.7 μm band and broader constraints remain largely unchanged.

Conclusions – Mid-infrared spectra representative of LIFE observations at $R = 100$ and $S/N \geq 10$ can robustly constrain key atmospheric and planetary properties of early Earth analogs, allowing detections of several potential prebiosignatures under favorable conditions. However, degeneracies involving H₂O, CO₂, and the thermal structure remain a major limitation. For the studied cases, focusing on the 6–18.5 μm range is sufficient, while improving the parametrization of the water profile will be crucial for more accurate retrievals in future studies.

Keywords: methods: statistical – planets and satellites: terrestrial planets – planets and satellites: atmospheres

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	General Context	1
1.2	Project Specific Background	2
2	Methods	4
2.1	Input Spectra	4
2.1.1	Opacity Datasets	5
2.2	Simulating Observations with LIFEsim	6
2.3	PyRetLIFE: The Retrieval Framework	6
2.3.1	Water Profile Calculation	8
2.4	Evaluation Metrics	9
2.4.1	Inspection of the Posterior	9
2.4.2	The Bayes Ratio	10
2.4.3	The Prior-Normalized Root-Mean-Squared Error (RMSE)	10
3	Results and Discussion	12
3.1	The Non-Dry Models	12
3.1.1	Retrieved Fluxes	12
3.1.2	Pressure-Temperature Profiles	14
3.1.3	Physical Parameters	15
3.1.4	Atmospheric Parameters	16
3.1.5	Water Profiles	18
3.2	The Dry Models	20
3.3	Impact of the 4–6 μm Range	23
3.3.1	CO Detectability	24
3.3.2	Impact on Other Molecules	25
3.3.3	Implications for LIFE	25
4	Conclusions and Outlook	27
4.1	Conclusion	27
4.2	Outlook	29
	Acknowledgments	31
A	Supplementary Data from the Retrievals	39
B	Validation of the Framework with a Broader Molecular Set	42
C	Fixed P-T Profile Retrievals	45

1 Introduction

Ever since the discovery of the first exoplanet, *51 Pegasi b*, by [Mayor and Queloz \(1995\)](#), exoplanetary science has progressed from the discovery of hot Jupiters to the identification of rocky exoplanets orbiting in the habitable zones of nearby stars. As the field grew, the focus moved from the detection of exoplanets to the detailed characterization of their properties, in particular their atmospheres, with the hope of unraveling the mysteries of life beyond Earth. This thesis is intended as a modest step forward in the search for prebiosignatures, the very stepping stones of life.

1.1 General Context

The search for life beyond Earth is closely tied to the study of planetary atmospheres, as they can preserve chemical fingerprints of biological or abiotic processes. In this framework, we define biosignatures as atmospheric species, or combinations of species, whose presence could indicate biological activity. Classical examples include molecular oxygen (O_2), nitrous oxide (N_2O), and methane (CH_4), especially when detected together in chemical disequilibrium. A broader range of molecules relevant to this research are prebiosignatures, meaning molecules that may not directly indicate life, but play a key role in prebiotic chemistry.

Previous works have already explored the connection between planetary atmospheres and prebiotic chemistry. For instance, [Rimmer et al. \(2019\)](#) studied the photochemical production of hydrogen cyanide (HCN) in nitrogen-rich exoplanet atmospheres, showing that HCN can form efficiently and may act as a universal feedstock for prebiotic chemistry. Building on this, [Pearce et al. \(2022\)](#) demonstrated how atmospheric HCN in early-Earth scenarios could have rained onto the surface and fueled the synthesis of nucleotide precursors, thereby supporting the RNA world hypothesis. More recently, [Claringbold et al. \(2023\)](#) quantified the detectability of a suite of prebiosignatures, including HCN, H_2S , C_2H_2 , CH_4 , NO, SO_2 , and CO, in exoplanetary atmospheres with JWST, providing a systematic framework for assessing the astronomical testability of prebiotic pathways. In this work, we build on these studies by investigating the detectability of HCN, H_2S , NO, CH_4 , C_2H_2 , SO_2 , H_2O , and CO in early-Earth scenarios, focusing on their observability in the mid-infrared, in the context of the Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE), a mission concept led by the Quanz group at ETH Zürich ([Quanz et al. 2022](#)).

Detecting and quantifying these molecules requires high-quality spectra across the relevant wavelength ranges. Current observatories, most notably the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), have already demonstrated the feasibility of atmospheric spectroscopy and provided the first insights into the atmospheres of exoplanets. However, their sensitivity and wavelength coverage are not optimized for a systematic search for biosignatures on Earth-sized planets. Future dedicated missions are therefore essential to address this challenge ([Seager et al. 2025](#)). Aside from LIFE, discussed in depth in Section 1.2, several other missions have been studied. On the ground, the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) ([Padovani et al. 2023](#)) will advance exoplanetary

science through direct imaging and spectroscopic characterization of nearby planetary systems, while for space-based missions several concepts such as LUVOIR (Peterson et al. 2017) and HabEx (Gaudi et al. 2020) have been proposed. While LUVOIR and HabEx remain mission concepts, they have served as the foundation for NASA’s Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO) (Bolcar et al. 2025), which aims to directly image and characterize rocky temperate exoplanets by observing across a wide wavelength range, from ultraviolet to the near-infrared. As shown by Alei et al. (2024), the synergy between HWO and LIFE can be of great benefit for exoplanetary science.

In the following section, we discuss the specifics of the LIFE mission, introduce the concept of retrievals, and outline the questions we aim to answer with this work.

1.2 Project Specific Background

The design for LIFE is based upon the concept of nulling interferometry (Bracewell 1978), which allows for the direct observation of exoplanets by suppressing the light from their host star. The mission aims to combine direct imaging with mid-infrared spectroscopy to study terrestrial planets around nearby stars. This wavelength range contains strong features of many relevant biosignatures and prebiosignature molecules, making LIFE particularly well-suited for assessing the conditions for habitability and the potential presence of life.

The exact wavelength range for LIFE is the subject of ongoing studies, with no definitive answer. On the science side, Konrad et al. (2022) argue that an optimal range of 4–18.5 μm maximizes retrieval performance, and while this range remains the baseline, Konrad et al. (2024) show that a restricted range of 6–16 μm might not significantly hinder the science case, calling for further investigation. From an instrumentation point of view, the broader 4–18.5 μm coverage presents additional challenges, and Glauser et al. (2024) presents 6–16 μm as the requirement, with 4–18.5 μm indicated as the goal. In this work we adhere to the 4–18.5 μm range for our main analysis, and subsequently explore the impact that excluding the 4–6 μm range might have on the retrieval of atmospheric abundances. This range includes the 4.7 μm CO band and removing it from our wavelength coverage prevents reliable constraints on CO abundances, limiting our ability to identify this important anti-biosignature. Another important factor is the spectral resolution R , which indicates how finely we can separate adjacent wavelengths. In this work, we adopt $R = 100$, consistent with the baseline design studies for LIFE (Glauser et al. 2024).

Beyond the wavelength coverage and the spectral resolution, the scientific return of LIFE depends critically on our ability to interpret the observed spectra. This is achieved through retrievals, a Bayesian analysis framework in which noisy data are statistically compared with forward models to infer atmospheric and planetary properties (Madhusudhan 2019). Retrievals combine our prior knowledge of model parameters with observations, producing posterior probability distributions that describe the most likely atmospheric states and their associated uncertainties. In practice, retrieval frameworks are composed of a forward model that simulates spectral observations based on a set of input parameters, and a sampling algorithm that systematically explores the parameter space and updates the parameter set. At each iteration the output of the forward model is compared to the observed spectrum via a likelihood function that

quantifies the discrepancy between the two. The likelihood then informs the sampler about how well a given parameter set explains the data, guiding it toward regions of higher probability. In successive iterations, the sampler proposes improved parameter sets, and this process continues until the parameter space has been thoroughly explored and the posterior probability distributions are mapped out. This method allows us to not only determine whether atmospheric and physical parameters are detectable, but also to quantify uncertainties, reveal degeneracies, and test the robustness of atmospheric inferences.

This study focuses on early-Earth scenarios, with the goal of understanding if LIFE can robustly retrieve the abundances of prebiotic signatures. Moreover, we explore the consequences of restricting the wavelength coverage by removing the 4–6 μm range, focusing primarily, though not exclusively, on CO. Answering these questions allows us to assess both the detectability of specific molecules in early-Earth scenarios and the robustness of the retrieval framework itself. More broadly, the results contribute to the ongoing discussion of optimal wavelength coverage and observing strategies for LIFE, and to the readiness of retrieval techniques for the characterization of temperate terrestrial exoplanets.

In the following chapter we describe the input spectra, simulation tools, retrieval methodology and the statistical tools we use in our analysis. Chapter 3 presents and interprets the retrieval results, discussing their implications for LIFE. Finally, Chapter 4 summarizes our conclusions and provides an outlook for future work.

2 Methods

In this chapter we describe the methodology used to investigate the detectability of prebiosignatures with LIFE. We introduce the simulated spectra used in the analysis and explain the relevance of the chosen atmospheric compositions. We then discuss the use of LIFEsim (Dannert et al. 2022) to calculate the noise profile, and we introduce the retrieval framework PyRetLIFE (Konrad et al. 2022)¹. Finally, we explain how we evaluated the results in a qualitative and quantitative manner.

2.1 Input Spectra

To study LIFE’s ability to detect prebiosignatures we used simulated exoplanetary emission spectra. This allowed us to have true values for the retrieved parameters, which means we can evaluate the retrieval outputs against the simulated flux inputs. The synthetic spectra serving as inputs were generated by Alastair Claringbold and Paul Rimmer specifically for this study (private communication).

These emission spectra were simulated with a 1D radiative transfer model implemented using petitRADTRANS (Mollière et al. 2019). For the model planetary system, we considered an Earth-twin around a solar analog. For the pressure-temperature profile, we used the 3.9 Gyr solar host model from Rugheimer et al. (2018), and for the water profile we used the August-Roche-Magnus formula from Alduchov et al. (1996).

For the *Null* scenario, our base case, we used the Hadean atmosphere of Kasting (1990) with the updated H₂ abundance from Zahnle et al. (2019), adopting the following volume mixing ratios (VMR): 70% N₂, 20% CO₂, 5% CO, and 5% H₂, with H₂O set by vapour pressure equilibrium. To model the impact of prebiosignatures we created

Model	H ₂ O	CO	H ₂ S	HCN	SO ₂	CH ₄	NO	C ₂ H ₂
■ Null	v. p. eq.	0.05	–	–	–	–	–	–
■ Null Dry	10 ⁻⁶	0.05	–	–	–	–	–	–
■ Cyanosulfidic	v. p. eq.	0.05	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	–	–	–
■ Cyanosulfidic Dry	10 ⁻⁶	0.05	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	–	–	–
■ Prebiotic Paradise	v. p. eq.	0.05	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁴	–	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁴

Table 2.1: Atmospheric compositions (volume mixing ratios) used for the five simulated exoplanetary atmospheres. All models use the Zahnle update of the Kasting Earth background (Zahnle et al. 2019; Kasting 1990): 70% N₂, 20% CO₂, 5% CO, and 5% H₂. H₂O is set by vapor pressure equilibrium (v. p. eq.) unless noted as “Dry” (fixed to 1 ppm).

two additional scenarios: *Cyanosulfidic* and *Prebiotic Paradise*. In the first scenario, we include vertically uniform abundances of 10 ppm HCN, H₂S, and SO₂ to the base atmosphere, motivated by the chemical pathways described in Patel et al. (2015). The second scenario explores a more extreme prebiotic chemistry case, adding 100 ppm

¹This name was not used in the publication, but it has been used internally to refer to the framework.

HCN, H₂S, NO, CH₄, and C₂H₂ to the control atmosphere. We also include dry versions of both the *Null* and *Cyanosulfidic* models to assess the impact of water vapor on the detectability of prebiosignatures. In these two cases water is set at a vertically uniform abundance of 1 ppm. The atmospheric compositions of the models can be found in Table 2.1.

The wavelength coverage of these spectra is 4–18.5 μm calculated at a resolution of $R = 1000$ and rebinned to $R = 100$ to match the minimal requirement discussed in Section 1.2. In Figure 2.1, the fluxes of all models are plotted to illustrate the spectral differences between the five atmospheric scenarios. Together, these five scenarios cover

Figure 2.1: Simulated emission spectra for the five atmospheric scenarios considered in this work: *Null*, *Null Dry*, *Cyanosulfidic*, *Cyanosulfidic Dry*, and *Prebiotic Paradise*. The spectra are shown at a resolution of $R = 100$, scaled to a distance of 10 pc, and expressed in units of $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{Hz}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$.

a wide range of atmospheric states, which allow us to systematically assess LIFE’s sensitivity to prebiosignatures under early Earth conditions. The emphasis on CO-rich atmospheres provides an “ideal” test case for CO detectability which, as discussed in Section 3.3, has proved to be an appropriate choice to study the impact of the 4–6 μm range.

2.1.1 Opacity Datasets

For the simulated spectra we used the opacity datasets adopted in Claringbold et al. (2023), which are primarily based on the ExoMol database (Tennyson et al. 2016). In contrast, our retrieval analysis employs the HITRAN 2020 database (Gordon et al. 2022). This discrepancy between the forward-model (retrieval) and input (simulation) opacities can lead to minor differences in line positions and intensities. We discuss these discrepancies in Section 3.1.1. Table 2.2 summarizes the specific opacity sources used for each molecule, as well as for collision-induced absorption (CIA), in both cases.

Molecule / CIA Pair	Retrieval Opacities	Simulation Opacities
H ₂ O	Conway et al. (2020)	Rothman et al. (2010)
CO ₂	Tashkun et al. (2019)	Yurchenko et al. (2020)
CO	Li et al. (2015)	Rothman et al. (2010)
CH ₄	Hargreaves et al. (2020)	Yurchenko et al. (2017)
H ₂ S	Azzam et al. (2016)	Azzam et al. (2016)
HCN	Barber et al. (2014)	Barber et al. (2014)
SO ₂	Gordon et al. (2022)	Underwood et al. (2016)
NO	Wong et al. (2017)	Wong et al. (2017)
C ₂ H ₂	Amyay et al. (2016)	Chubb et al. (2020)
N ₂ -N ₂ (CIA)	Richard et al. (2012)	Richard et al. (2012)

Table 2.2: Opacity data sources for each molecule and CIA process. The first column lists the opacity sources used in the retrievals, and the second column lists those used in the simulation of the exoplanetary spectra.

2.2 Simulating Observations with LIFEsim

A necessary step in order to properly operate the retrieval framework is the simulation of realistic noise. This can be done using LIFEsim, a package developed to simulate observations of exoplanetary systems with LIFE (Dannert et al. 2022). LIFEsim models the observation as seen by LIFE and computes the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) as a function of the instrument characteristics, target properties and observation time. The simulator assumes photon-noise dominated observations, and accounts for the dominant astrophysical noise sources such as stellar leakage, local zodiacal emission, and exozodiacal emission, but does not yet include instrumental noise terms. Additionally, it applies a detector quantum efficiency of $\eta_{QE} = 0.7$ and an instrumental throughput of $\eta_t = 0.05$, resulting in an effective detection efficiency of $\eta = 0.035$.

In this work, we use LIFEsim to add realistic astrophysical noise to the simulated spectra described in Section 2.1. We define the global S/N at the reference wavelength of 11.2 μm following the convention of previous works (Konrad et al. 2022; Alei et al. 2022). This specific wavelength was chosen because it does not coincide with strong absorption bands and therefore probes the planetary continuum emission. The noisy spectra produced by LIFEsim serve as a direct input to the retrieval framework described in Section 2.3. An example of the application of this noise to one of the input spectra can be seen in Figure 2.2.

2.3 PyRetLIFE: The Retrieval Framework

PyRetLIFE is a Bayesian framework for atmospheric retrievals developed by the Quanz Group at ETH and first introduced in Konrad et al. (2022). It couples petitRADTRANS to the nested sampler PyMultiNest (Buchner et al. 2014) to infer atmospheric and planetary parameters from the noisy spectra produced in Section 2.2. petitRADTRANS computes the planetary emission spectrum using the model parameters sampled by

Figure 2.2: Flux of the Null Dry model at three different stages of processing. The top panel shows the original top-of-atmosphere (TOA) flux at a resolution of $R = 1000$, the central panel shows the same flux rebinned to $R = 100$ and scaled to an observer at 10 pc, and the bottom panel shows the same flux with an S/N of 10 at $11.2 \mu\text{m}$, calculated using *LIFEsim*.

PyMultiNest, which is then rebinned to the LIFE working resolution and wavelength range, and scaled to a distance of 10 pc to match the simulated observations. These spectra are then compared to the original inputs of the framework through the Gaussian likelihood

$$\ln(\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta})) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{(D_i - \mu_i(\boldsymbol{\theta}))^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right], \quad (2.1)$$

where D_i are the input spectra discussed in Section 2.2, σ_i the *LIFEsim* noise at wavelength bin i , and $\mu_i(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ are the values produced by *petitRADTRANS* using the sampled parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^2$.

We adopt the priors as shown in Table 2.3 following [Konrad et al. \(2024\)](#). We parameterize the P–T profile as a fourth-degree polynomial, with the coefficients a_i treated as retrieval parameters. This parametrization has been shown to flexibly capture the thermal structures of Earth-like planets while remaining computationally efficient ([Alej et al. 2024](#); [Konrad et al. 2024](#)). The molecular abundance priors are implemented with

²Here we interpret the output of *petitRADTRANS* as the mean of the distribution from which the data points D_i are drawn. This interpretation is a key step in Bayesian analysis, as it allows us to define the likelihood that the D_i are realizations of that distribution.

a log-uniform distribution to capture a wide range of possible atmospheric compositions. For both the planetary radius R_{pl} and the planetary mass $\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}})$, we assume Gaussian priors. The prior on R_{pl} follows [Dannert et al. \(2022\)](#), who showed that an initial radius estimate can be obtained from a planet’s detection with LIFE. Using this estimate together with the FORECASTER mass–radius relation ([Chen et al. 2016](#)), we then derive the corresponding prior for $\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}})$. Posterior sampling and Bayesian

Parameter	Prior	Description
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	$\mathcal{G}(1, 0.2)$	Planetary radius
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	$\mathcal{G}(0, 0.4)$	Planetary mass
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	$\mathcal{U}(-4, 2)$	Surface pressure
a_0	$\mathcal{U}(0, 500)$	P-T parameter of degree 0
a_1	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1000)$	P-T parameter of degree 1
a_2	$\mathcal{U}(0, 500)$	P-T parameter of degree 2
a_3	$\mathcal{U}(0, 100)$	P-T parameter of degree 3
a_4	$\mathcal{U}(0, 20)$	P-T parameter of degree 4
$\log_{10}(X_i)$	$\mathcal{U}(-10, 0)$	VMR for each retrieved molecule
$\log_{10}(\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$	$\mathcal{U}(-5, 0)$	Water drying parameter

Table 2.3: Prior distributions used in all retrievals. The $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ indicates a uniform distribution from a to b , and $\mathcal{G}(\mu, \sigma)$ indicates a Gaussian distribution with mean μ and standard deviation σ .

evidences \mathcal{Z} are obtained with PyMultiNest. We use the default PyRetLIFE value of 600 live points, and the default PyMultiNest evidence tolerance and sampling efficiency of 0.5 and 0.8 respectively. The evidences are used for model comparison and to quantify detection as explained in Section 2.4.

2.3.1 Water Profile Calculation

As mentioned in Section 2.1, the non-dry models adopt a variable H_2O profile rather than a vertically constant abundance. It was shown in [Konrad et al. \(2024\)](#) that capturing this behavior significantly improves the quality of the retrievals, and here we briefly discuss how it was implemented. The implementation begins by assuming a constant H_2O volume mixing ratio and using it to compute the corresponding water partial pressure in each atmospheric layer. The saturation vapor pressure in each layer is then calculated from the local temperature using the Goff–Gratch equations ([Goff and Gratch 1946](#); [Goff 1957](#)) (over water or over ice depending on the temperature). Then, beginning from the lowest layer, we compare the partial pressure with the saturation pressure to determine whether condensation occurs: if the H_2O partial pressure remains below saturation the profile is unchanged, but if it exceeds saturation, the H_2O abundance in that and all higher layers is reduced so that the partial pressure equals the saturation value. Continuing upward, any remaining supersaturation is trimmed layer by layer. This produces a profile that is constant with altitude until condensation sets in, and then monotonically decreases as we move upwards. Because this scheme tends to overestimate water in the dry upper atmosphere, the framework also includes an additional “drying” parameter $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. This parameter scales the H_2O amount in the

upper atmosphere, enabling the retrieval to capture the much drier conditions observed there.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate our retrievals and assess their performance, we combine qualitative and quantitative metrics. For a general evaluation of the performance across all parameters we inspect the posteriors, visually checking whether the parameters are both constrained and consistent with the true values. For specific parameters (such as CO) we introduce the Bayes ratio, which allows us to quantify the detection significance of the target parameter by comparing models with and without said parameter. To measure bias and variance relative to the true values we use the root-mean-squared error (RMSE), following [Alej et al. \(2024\)](#).

2.4.1 Inspection of the Posterior

Visually evaluating the posterior distributions of the parameters of a retrieval is a widely used approach in Bayesian analysis, which allows us to assess whether a parameter is well constrained (narrow posterior) or unconstrained (broad posterior), and whether the distribution is centered around the true value of the input spectra. In particular a multimodal, skewed or flat posterior can indicate a lack of constraining power in the data or a degeneracy between different parameters. To visualize posteriors we implement corner plots, which display both the 1D distributions of a single parameter as well as the 2D projections of all parameter pairs. From the 1D posterior we can evaluate whether the parameter is constrained, while from the 2D distributions we can identify correlations and degeneracies between pairs of parameters.

A formalized version of the visual inspection of the 1D posterior approach was introduced in Appendix B of [Konrad et al. \(2022\)](#). The posteriors were classified in four categories: unconstrained (UC), upper limit (UL), sensitivity limit (SL), and constrained (C), by fitting analytic functions to the posterior distributions and selecting the best fitting model. This scheme provides a systematic way to translate the visual impression into a reproducible diagnostic. In this work we adopt the same four categories, but implement the distinction between posterior types in a way that best reflects the behavior of our retrievals. In Figure 2.3 we show the four different posterior categories with the best fit analytic function. The UC posterior type indicates that

Figure 2.3: Example of each posterior type in order from least to best constrained. Below each figure we see the way they will be represented in the results section, such as [Figures 3.4](#) and [3.9](#).

the data provide essentially no information about the parameter. The UL posterior type decreases towards high values, indicating that we cannot measure the parameter

directly, but we can place an upper bound on its value. For the SL posterior type we see a flat tail at low values before turning into a Gaussian-like distribution above a transition point. This indicates that the data begin to constrain the parameter only once it is above the transition point. The C posterior type is well described by a Gaussian, indicating that the data provide a reliable measurement of the parameter.

2.4.2 The Bayes Ratio

The Bayesian evidence \mathcal{Z}_i of a model \mathcal{M}_i with parameters θ_i is the integral of the likelihood \mathcal{L} over the priors π :

$$\mathcal{Z}_i(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{M}_i) = \int \mathcal{L}(\theta_i)\pi(\theta_i)d\theta_i. \quad (2.2)$$

This quantity represents how well the model as a whole explains the data³. The Bayes ratio κ is a metric used to compare two models \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 by making use of their Bayesian evidences. It establishes which model provides the best balance between goodness of fit and model complexity, and is calculated according to:

$$\kappa = \frac{\mathcal{Z}_1(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{M}_1)}{\mathcal{Z}_2(\mathcal{D}|\mathcal{M}_2)}. \quad (2.3)$$

For our purposes, the Bayes ratio can be used to establish if the presence of a given molecule is supported by the data. We do so by taking \mathcal{M}_1 to be the model that includes the target molecule, and \mathcal{M}_2 the one that does not. To quantify whether the molecule’s presence is supported by the data, and how strongly, we can use the Jeffreys scale (Jeffreys 1998) reported in Table 2.4.

Range of κ	Support for \mathcal{M}_1
$\kappa < 1$	Not supported by the data
$1 < \kappa < 10^{0.5}$	Very weak support
$10^{0.5} \leq \kappa < 10^1$	Substantial support
$10^1 \leq \kappa < 10^2$	Strong support
$\kappa \geq 10^2$	Decisive support

Table 2.4: Jeffreys scale for interpreting the Bayes ratio κ , indicating the degree of support for \mathcal{M}_1 .

2.4.3 The Prior-Normalized Root-Mean-Squared Error (RMSE)

Since we are working with simulated spectra, we can exploit the knowledge of the true parameter values to assess the quality of the retrieved posteriors. For each parameter θ , we consider the posterior mean μ , the standard deviation σ , and the true value τ . To

³While the likelihood \mathcal{L} quantifies how well the model explains the data when evaluated at its best fit parameters, weighting it over the prior space tells us how well the model itself (independent of parameters) explains the data. So \mathcal{Z} balances both the quality of the best fit and the complexity of the model.

quantify the combined effects of bias and uncertainty, we compute a prior-normalized root-mean-squared error (RMSE) defined as

$$\text{RMSE}(\theta) = \frac{\sqrt{(\mu - \tau)^2 + \sigma^2}}{W_{\text{prior}}}, \quad (2.4)$$

where W_{prior} is the prior width. For log-Gaussian parameters we adopt $W_{\text{prior}} = 5\sigma_{\text{prior}}$.

This normalization allows for direct comparison of retrieval performance across parameters with different units or scales. A low RMSE indicates that the retrieval is both accurate and precise, whereas a high value signals either systematic biases or weakly constrained parameters. Although there is no absolute scale by which to assess retrieval quality using RMSE, it remains a useful metric for comparing how different models perform for a given parameter.

3 Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we present the outcomes of the retrieval analysis for the different atmospheric scenarios. The analysis was performed at three S/N levels: 10, 20, and 50. The first two represent realistic regimes, with S/N = 20 on the higher end, while S/N = 50 corresponds to an idealized case used to explore the potential and limitations of PyRetLIFE. We divide the five models into dry and non-dry cases to facilitate comparison across scenarios. Finally, we investigate CO detectability in Section 3.3.

3.1 The Non-Dry Models

In this section, we analyze the retrievals of the three non-dry atmospheric scenarios introduced in Section 2.1: *Null*, *Cyanosulfidic*, and *Prebiotic Paradise*. The *Null* model represents a simple atmospheric baseline, while the *Cyanosulfidic* and *Prebiotic Paradise* cases progressively include higher abundances of prebiotic molecules. Together, they provide a gradient in chemical complexity against which to test retrieval performance.

We evaluate the results by examining four key aspects: the retrieved fluxes in Section 3.1.1, the thermal structure in Section 3.1.2, the physical parameters in Section 3.1.3, and the atmospheric composition in Section 3.1.4 with a specific focus on vertical water vapor distribution in Section 3.1.5. Our goal is to identify which features of the atmosphere are robustly constrained, which remain uncertain, and whether deviations from the input values arise from genuine physical effects or from limitations of the retrieval framework.

3.1.1 Retrieved Fluxes

In this section, we discuss the retrieved fluxes for the *Null*, *Cyanosulfidic* and *Prebiotic Paradise* scenarios. The results are displayed in Figure 3.1, alongside the true values and the LIFESim noise calculated according to Section 2.2. We display only the S/N = 10 case since it is the highest noise we consider and therefore the most challenging for our retrieval framework. If our flux retrievals are successful here, they will be successful at higher S/N as well.

As we can see, in all cases the retrieved flux lies within the noise level, certifying the consistency of our retrieval framework; but some minor deviations from the input spectra are worth noting. In particular, a spurious peak appears in all three models around 15 μm , which corresponds to the main CO₂ band and was also observed and discussed in Alei et al. (2022). Small mismatches are visible near 8 μm for the *Null* and *Cyanosulfidic* cases, and boundary effects are apparent beyond 18 μm in the *Null* and *Prebiotic Paradise* models. These long-wavelength deviations are also visible in the top panel of Figure 2.2, which shows the $R = 1000$ fluxes, but they disappear after rebinning, indicating that they arise from genuine atmospheric features rather than from numerical noise. Overall, these discrepancies remain within the observational uncertainties and are therefore not statistically significant, but they highlight how

deviations can arise in retrievals, either due to noise fluctuations or to limitations of the forward model at the spectral edges. In addition, small residuals may also stem from differences between the line lists used for the simulated and retrieved spectra (see Section 2.1.1), as minor inconsistencies in line positions or intensities can translate into subtle spectral mismatches. Such effects underscore the importance of examining the retrieved parameters in order to assess the physical robustness of the results.

Figure 3.1: Retrieved spectra for the three non-dry atmospheric scenarios: a *Null*, b *Cyanosulfidic*, and c *Paradise*. The black curve shows the input spectrum at 10 pc and the gray envelope shows the *LIFESim* simulated noise of $S/N = 10$. The colored bands indicate the central 90 %, 70 %, 50 %, and 30 % posterior predictive intervals.

The posterior predictive intervals further confirm the consistency of the retrieval framework: the progressively narrower shaded bands (90 %, 70 %, 50 %, and 30 %) correctly track the increasing confidence around the median spectrum and remain compatible with the simulated noise level across all wavelengths. Importantly, however, fluxes alone cannot be used to discriminate between atmospheric scenarios as they are

subject to degeneracies: distinct parameter combinations can reproduce indistinguishable fluxes. From the perspective of LIFE, this result indicates that broad spectral features can be robustly reproduced at $S/N = 10$, while the identification of specific molecular signatures requires the deeper parameter analysis presented in the following subsections.

Having established the success of PyRetLIFE in reproducing the input fluxes within the noise level, we move to the atmospheric and physical parameters to assess whether the retrievals recovered the original truth values.

3.1.2 Pressure-Temperature Profiles

We now examine the P-T profile, focusing the analysis on the $S/N = 10$ case for the same reasons as explained in Section 3.1.1. The posteriors and the truth values for the three models are shown in Figure 3.2. We restrict the minimum pressure to 10^{-4} bar which matches previous studies (Alej et al. 2024; Konrad et al. 2024). This choice reflects the fact that the infrared photosphere, i.e. the atmospheric layer where the observed infrared photons are emitted, lies at higher pressures. It is apparent that the surface pressure P_0 and the surface temperature T_0 are slightly overestimated at this S/N level. We discuss this overestimation in Section 3.1.3.

Figure 3.2: Retrieved pressure-temperature profiles for the three non-dry atmospheric models: Null, Cyanosulfidic, and Paradise for an S/N of 10. The solid black line shows the true input profile. Shaded regions represent credible intervals of 90 %, 70 %, 50 %, and 30 %.

Overall, the retrievals provide moderate constraints on the vertical temperature structure at this noise level. The posterior distributions constrain the temperature well across the pressures that dominate the MIR emission, but only partially follow the true profile. Constraints are strongest in the deeper atmosphere and progressively weaken with altitude. Above about 10^{-2} bar, the intervals widen rapidly, reflecting the loss of sensitivity once we are above the infrared photosphere. Additionally, degeneracies between the P-T profile and the molecular abundances, in which similar spectral signatures can arise from different combinations of temperature and composition, further broaden the posteriors.

Part of the discrepancy between the retrieved and true profiles can also be attributed to the parametrization adopted in our model. As discussed in [Konrad et al. \(2022\)](#), the P–T structure is represented by a fourth-degree polynomial, which is inherently unable to reproduce the true profile used in the simulations. We explore the implications of fixing the P–T profile in Appendix C.

These results contrast partially with the flux analysis: while the fluxes can be reproduced within the noise already at $S/N = 10$, the P–T structure is not reliably retrieved under the same conditions. This highlights the limited information content of the spectra with respect to the vertical thermal structure, and motivates the analysis of the physical parameters and water profiles in the following sections.

3.1.3 Physical Parameters

In this section, we analyze the posteriors for R_{pl} , M_{pl} , P_0 , and the surface temperature T_0 . While the latter is not an independent parameter in our framework, we extrapolate its posterior from the lowest atmospheric layer of the P–T profile, corresponding to the ground pressure P_0 . The values for the non-dry models at S/N 10, 20, and 50 can be seen in Figure 3.3 alongside their prior.

Figure 3.3: Retrieved parameter constraints for the three non-dry atmospheric models (Null, Cyanosulfidic, and Prebiotic Paradise) at $S/N = 10, 20,$ and 50 . Each colored line shows the 16th–84th percentile interval, with the marker indicating the posterior median. Different marker styles distinguish the S/N levels. Colors correspond to atmospheric models, while black lines represent the priors. Vertical lines mark the true values, and shaded regions denote tolerance bands of $\pm 0.2 R_{\oplus}$, $\pm 0.5 M_{\oplus}$, $\pm 0.5 \text{ dex}$, and $\pm 15 \text{ K}$ around them.

The radius is well constrained already at the lowest S/N value of 10, as the true value lies within the 16th–84th percentile interval and the posterior is noticeably narrower than the prior. We notice a weak bias toward lower values, which improves with increasing S/N .

The mass remains prior-dominated for the two lowest S/N values, as the posterior and the prior width are visually very similar. At $S/N = 50$ we see a narrower posterior, but with a significant offset from the true value in all three models. This systematic underestimation of the mass was already observed in [Konrad et al. \(2022\)](#) and was linked to the gravity-abundances degeneracy. This degeneracy originates from the fact that the same spectral features can arise from multiple combinations of mass and

atmospheric composition. While spectral features are sensitive to many parameters, one important factor is the optical depth, which under hydrostatic equilibrium can be written as

$$d\tau_\lambda = \sum_i -\frac{f_i}{\mu g} \sigma_{i,\lambda} dP, \quad (3.1)$$

where f_i is the volume mixing ratio (VMR) of species i , $\sigma_{i,\lambda}$ its absorption cross section, μ the mean molecular weight, and g the surface gravity. Optical depth is a relevant quantity because it sets the location of the effective photosphere at each wavelength, which in turn defines the observed spectrum. Retrievals therefore constrain τ_λ rather than the underlying f_i , μ , or g individually. This equation illustrates how different combinations of abundances, mean molecular weight, and gravity can yield the same optical depth, highlighting the degeneracy between mass (via g) and atmospheric composition (via μ and f_i). According to this analysis, a systematically underestimated mass should be compensated by an overestimation of the heavier and/or more abundant atmospheric components. We discuss this more in depth in Section 3.1.4.

The surface pressure is well constrained already at S/N 10 for all models, with a shift to lower values in the *Null* and *Cyanosulfidic* models as S/N increases. The prior is not shown in Figure 3.3 as it is too broad (see Table 2.3).

T_0 is well constrained at all S/N levels for both the *Null* and *Paradise* models, with differences between the posterior median and the true value of only a few K. For the *Cyanosulfidic* model however, the posteriors are significantly wider for S/N 10 and 20. This likely stems from the presence of SO_2 , whose wide absorption band between 8 and 10 μm covers the continuum emission and prevents a more accurate probe of the surface conditions. The *Paradise* model doesn't suffer from this issue as there is no SO_2 , and its additional absorbers produce narrower features that leave some continuum points visible, so T_0 remains better constrained.

3.1.4 Atmospheric Parameters

In this section, we discuss the posteriors for the retrieved molecules, which are shown in Figure 3.4. We do not display the posterior for H_2O , as in the non-dry models we retrieve a variable water profile, which is discussed in detail in Section 3.1.5.

N_2 , CO and H_2 : For N_2 and CO we see that for all models at all S/N the posteriors are unconstrained. This result was expected considering their very weak absorption in this wavelength range. For CO we run a deeper analysis and discuss the implications for LIFE in Section 3.3. Another weak absorber is H_2 , which remains unconstrained at S/N = 10 across all models but for which we can place an upper limit at higher S/N. However, this upper limit lies more than 0.5 dex above the true abundance of 5% VMR (corresponding to an H_2 fraction of roughly 16%) and therefore offers limited information on the atmospheric composition.

CO_2 : CO_2 is constrained across all three models, as the posteriors are all of type C and lie within the ± 0.5 dex band at all S/N levels. In the *Null* case there is a noticeable overestimation of the CO_2 VMR, which is also present to a lesser extent in the *Cyanosulfidic* case. This pattern is consistent with the gravity-abundances degeneracy

Figure 3.4: Posterior distributions for the three non-dry models (*Null*, *Cyanosulfidic*, and *Paradise*) for each retrieved species in VMR. Different markers indicate the S/N levels (10, 20, and 50), and colors correspond to the respective models. Vertical lines mark the true values, while the gray shaded areas represent ± 0.5 dex tolerance. When a molecule is absent in a model the corresponding band is left blank. For all posterior types, the 16th–84th percentile range is shown, except for upper-limit (UL) cases where the posterior is drawn from the 16th percentile to the upper limit.

discussed in Section 3.1.3: if M_p (hence g) is underestimated, the optical depth relation (Equation (3.1)) allows for a higher effective mean molecular weight μ . Considering CO_2 is the dominant μ -contributing species among the non trace constituents, its overestimation does not come as a surprise. In the *Paradise* model the CO_2 bias is muted, plausibly because additional bands from CH_4 , C_2H_2 , HCN , and NO provide anchors that reduce degeneracy with g .

Pairwise $M_{\text{p1}}\text{-CO}_2$ correlations remain weak in our corner plots (see Appendix A),

indicating that any residual trade-offs are distributed over the bulk composition and P-T parameters.

HCN: The results for HCN vary between the *Cyanosulfidic* and the *Paradise* model. In the *Paradise* case we see that we have SL type posterior across all S/N, with median values within the 0.5 dex band. This indicates that we can reliably provide an estimate of the HCN amount for the *Paradise* model. The same holds for the *Cyanosulfidic* model at S/N 50, but for the two lower values we have UL type posterior. The upper limit for the two UL posterior is more than 1 dex bigger than the true value for the *Cyanosulfidic* model, providing only very weak constraint.

H₂S: H₂S is present in the *Cyanosulfidic* and *Paradise* model, and for S/N of 10 and 20 only an upper limit can be provided for both cases, but with the *Cyanosulfidic* upper limit being within the ± 0.5 dex band and providing therefore a good measure of the true value. At S/N 50 posterior for the *Cyanosulfidic* model remains an UL type, while in the *Paradise* case the posterior is of type C with the true value inside the 16th-84th percentile band, allowing us to claim detection albeit with a slight underestimation in the median.

NO: NO appears only in the *Paradise* model, and is unconstrained at all S/N despite having a strong feature at around 5 μm . This likely reflects the weakness of the feature relative to other absorbers such as H₂O and CO₂.

CH₄: CH₄ is present only in the *Paradise* model and clearly constrained. Even at S/N = 10 the posterior is visibly narrow, with further tightening with increasing S/N. There is a slight underestimation in the lowest noise case, but the median is still well within the 0.5 dex band.

C₂H₂: C₂H₂ is present only in *Paradise*, with posteriors that decisively tighten with S/N. At S/N = 10 we have a SL type posterior with a wide Gaussian and a severe underestimation of the truth value. By S/N = 20 the posterior is still a SL type, but centered much nearer to the truth (at the lower border of the 0.5 dex band). At S/N 50 we have a decisive constraint, with a tight Gaussian posterior centered very precisely on the truth.

SO₂: SO₂ is unique to the *Cyanosulfidic* model, and is constrained (C) at all S/N values. The posterior is centered around the true values, allowing us to claim a confident detection. Despite the high mean molecular weight of SO₂, it remains a trace component and therefore contributes negligibly to the mean molecular weight. As a result, it does not strongly participate in the gravity-abundances degeneracy that produces the CO₂ offset, so its retrieved abundance shows no systematic bias.

3.1.5 Water Profiles

In the previous section, we intentionally omitted the posteriors for H₂O, as the water abundance in the non-dry models varies with altitude. The retrieved H₂O profiles

for the $S/N = 10$ case are shown in Figure 3.5, where the shaded regions represent the central credible intervals around the median, and the black line indicates the true profile used to generate the spectra. In all models, the retrieval constrains the profile

Figure 3.5: Retrieved vertical profiles of H_2O volume mixing ratio (VMR) for the three non-dry atmospheric models: Null, Cyanosulfidic, and Paradise. Shaded regions represent the central 90%, 70%, 50%, and 30% credible intervals around the posterior median. The black line shows the true H_2O profile used to generate the simulated spectra.

well for pressure levels above 10^{-2} bar, while for the higher atmospheric layers there is a clear deviation from the true profile. This difference is mostly attributed to the implementation of the water profile discussed in Section 2.3.1, where we explained how the water amount can only remain constant or decrease as we move up in the atmosphere. Considering the true water profile increases in the upper atmosphere, we have to account for the inability of our framework to capture this behavior. The threshold of 10^{-2} bar was also identified in Section 3.1.2 as the pressure level below which the P–T profile is better constrained. This was attributed to the location of the infrared photosphere near that level, and the fact that the same pattern appears in the H_2O profile for all three models further supports this interpretation. Because the water profile is correlated with the P–T structure, the small discrepancies between the true and retrieved P–T profiles seen in Figure 3.2 imply that a perfect reconstruction of the H_2O profile cannot be expected. The three models exhibit similar behavior overall, with slightly better constraints in the *Cyanosulfidic* case. These differences primarily reflect the extent to which other molecular species help anchor the H_2O profile.

At higher S/N , the retrievals follow the same trends as in the $S/N = 10$ case, with the main difference being narrower credible intervals. Additional plots are omitted for brevity.

Since the true water profile was derived from the true P–T profile using the August–Roche–Magnus equation, as described in Section 2.1, whereas `PyRetLIFE` employs the Goff–Gratch formulation, we performed a dedicated retrieval test using the August–Roche–Magnus relation to assess any potential discrepancies. None were found, indicating that this difference has no consequential impact on our analysis.

3.2 The Dry Models

In this section, we analyze the retrievals of the two dry atmospheric scenarios introduced in Section 2.1: *Null Dry* and *Cyanosulfidic Dry*. These models are constructed by suppressing water vapor to a uniform low abundance of 1 ppm. By comparing their results with the corresponding non-dry cases, we can isolate the impact of water on the retrieval of surface conditions, atmospheric parameters, and prebiosignature molecules. To avoid repetitions, we will focus on what differentiates these models from their non-dry counterparts, and on what confirms our analysis from Section 3.1.

Fluxes: The retrieved fluxes for the S/N 10 case are shown in Figure 3.6, and as in Figure 3.1 the posterior lies within the gray noise envelope. Here as well we notice both the upper boundary deviations in the *Null Dry* model, and the peak at $15\ \mu\text{m}$ (corresponding to the CO_2 band) in both models. As before, the fluxes are very well retrieved, so we move to the other results to evaluate the performance of our retrievals.

Figure 3.6: Retrieved spectra for the two dry atmospheric scenarios: a *Null Dry* and b *Cyanosulfidic Dry*. The black curve shows the input spectrum at 10 pc and the gray envelope shows the *LIFESim* simulated noise of S/N = 10. The colored bands indicate the central 90 %, 70 %, 50 %, and 30 % posterior predictive intervals.

P-T Profile and Physical Parameters: As before, both models reproduce the P-T behavior well below 10^{-2} bar, with the uncertainty increasing toward lower pressures. The posterior shapes of the two models closely mirror those of their non-dry

Figure 3.7: Retrieved pressure-temperature profiles for the two dry atmospheric models: *Null Dry* and *Cyanosulfidic Dry* for an S/N of 10. The solid black line shows the true input profile. Shaded regions represent credible intervals of 90 %, 70 %, 50 %, and 30 %.

counterparts, with the main differences occurring near the surface, where the dry models better capture the P-T structure at high pressures and more tightly constrain the surface conditions.

As shown in Figure 3.8, both P_0 and T_0 are indeed better constrained in the dry models, with narrower posteriors centered more closely on the true values. In particular, the surface temperature retrieval performs much better in the dry cases, with the largest improvement observed for the *Cyanosulfidic Dry* model: while in the *Cyanosulfidic* case T_0 was overestimated at all S/N levels, with broad posteriors at $S/N = 10$ and 20, the dry case already yields a 67 % credible interval within ± 10 K at $S/N = 10$, and the median value matches almost exactly the true temperature.

For the planetary radius, the retrievals show nearly identical behavior between dry and non-dry models, whereas noticeable differences arise in the inferred mass. In both dry cases, the posteriors are significantly broader across all S/N levels and appear prior-dominated. The systematic underestimation observed previously persists here as well and can once again be attributed to the gravity–abundance degeneracy.

Atmospheric Composition: The molecular abundances posteriors are shown in ??, where H_2O is included since its abundance is vertically constant in the dry models. For N_2 and CO , the behavior is identical to that of the non-dry models, with unconstrained posteriors at all S/N levels.

H_2 : In the *Null Dry* model, H_2 shows an upper limit (UL) posterior at $S/N = 50$ and unconstrained (UC) posteriors at lower S/N . In the corresponding non-dry case, the $S/N = 20$ posterior already transitions to UL type; however, this difference is not particularly significant, as the retrieved upper limit remains too high to provide a meaningful constraint. The *Cyan Dry* model exhibits an unexpected trend, with a UC posterior at $S/N = 50$ and UL posteriors at $S/N = 10$ and 20. This may result from the high true abundance of H_2 , which makes UL and UC type posteriors appear similar in

Figure 3.8: Retrieved parameter constraints for the two dry atmospheric models (*Null Dry* and *Cyanosulfidic Dry*) at S/N 10, 20, and 50. Each colored line shows the 16th–84th percentile interval, with the marker indicating the posterior median. Different marker styles distinguish the S/N levels. Colors correspond to atmospheric models, while black lines represent the priors. Vertical lines mark the true values, and shaded regions denote tolerance bands of $\pm 0.2 R_{\oplus}$, $\pm 0.5 M_{\oplus}$, ± 0.5 dex, and ± 15 K around them.

shape. As discussed in Section 3.1.4, these results are not critical for our study, since such a high upper limit does not yield a useful constraint on the abundance.

CO₂: For CO₂ we see the same overestimation as in the non-dry models, but in this case with slightly wider posteriors and a bigger median value. Both of these can be explained in the context of the gravity-abundances degeneracy. As the mass is less constrained, we indeed expect the mean molecular weight to be less constrained, and consequently CO₂ (the main contributor to μ) as well.

H₂O: In both models we see water well constrained at $S/N = 50$, but wider posteriors at lower S/N . In the *Null Dry* model we have UL and SL posteriors at S/N 10 and 20 respectively, while for the *Cyanosulfidic Dry* model both are UL posteriors. This indicates that we can place a weak constraint on H₂O at low S/N for dry atmospheres. The poor characterization of H₂O reflects all the same difficulties that we have encountered in the H₂O profile characterization in the non-dry cases, and should not be attributed to the low water abundance as it is a very powerful absorber.

HCN: The constraint on HCN improved substantially, with C type posteriors at both $S/N = 20$ and 50, while at $S/N = 10$ we see a very similar posterior as the non-dry *Cyanosulfidic* scenario. This improvement can be attributed to the scarcity of water, whose strong and frequent absorption bands can interfere with the detectability of other molecules in the non-dry models.

H₂S: H₂S posteriors remain UL type at all S/N , all with an upper limit within the ± 0.5 dex band. This is very similar to the non-dry models.

SO₂: SO₂ remains constrained across S/N , confirming the non-dry model results of a confident detection.

Figure 3.9: Posterior distributions for the two dry models (Null Dry and Cyanosulfidic Dry) for each retrieved species in VMR. Different markers indicate the S/N levels (10, 20, and 50), and colors correspond to the respective models. Vertical lines mark the true values, while the gray shaded areas represent ± 0.5 dex tolerance. When a molecule is absent in a model the corresponding band is left blank. For all posterior types, the 16th–84th percentile range is shown, except for upper-limit (UL) cases where the posterior is drawn from the 16th percentile to the upper limit.

In general we see very similar performance between the dry and non-dry models, with water abundance having only mild effects on the retrieval of other species. The dry cases have a better estimate of the surface conditions, likely due to the lack of strong water absorption that in the non-dry models obscures the continuum emission.

3.3 Impact of the 4–6 μm Range

In this section, we investigate the impact of reducing the wavelength range from the baseline 4–18.5 μm to 6–18.5 μm . Konrad et al. (2024) previously showed that the 4–6 μm interval provides no additional constraints or improvements in precision for an exo-Earth atmosphere. Here, we assess whether this result also holds for our early Earth scenarios. The molecules directly affected by this truncation are CO and NO, which

exhibit their primary absorption bands at 4.7 μm and 5.3 μm respectively. Because CO is often considered a potential anti-biosignature (Wang et al. 2016) and is present at high abundance in all of our models, our analysis focuses primarily on its detectability within this spectral range.

3.3.1 CO Detectability

In Sections 3.1 and 3.2 we have already shown how even at high S/N the posteriors for CO are unconstrained, meaning that including the 4.7 μm CO band in our wavelength range does not allow for the detection of CO. We confirm this using the Bayes ratio, as explained in Section 2.4. For this we denote our original models (the ones used in the previous sections) as \mathcal{M}_1 , and we construct for each scenario alternative models \mathcal{M}_2 that are identical to \mathcal{M}_1 except for the removal of CO as a parameter. This allows us to verify for each atmospheric scenario which model is preferred according to the Bayes ratio. The results reported in Figure 3.10 show for each scenario and S/N how strong the support for \mathcal{M}_1 is, meaning how strong the support is for the presence of CO. We see that for the *Cyanosulfidic*, *Cyanosulfidic Dry* and *Prebiotic Paradise* scenarios there is little to no support for the presence of CO. On the other hand, for the *Null* model, the presence of CO is strongly preferred at all S/N while for the *Null Dry* model only at S/N 50.

These results highlight an important distinction between detection and quantification. While the posterior distributions for CO remain unconstrained across all models and S/N, the Bayes factor can still prefer models that include CO. This preference arises in scenarios where CO is a significant background constituent, so in models such as *Null* and *Null Dry* with fewer atmospheric parameters. In these cases, removing CO changes the mean molecular weight and thus the optical depth, producing small but detectable differences in the continuum emission of the planet. By contrast, in the *Cyanosulfidic*, *Cyanosulfidic Dry* and *Prebiotic Paradise* models, the presence of additional strong absorbers dominates the spectra, such that CO has negligible impact and the Bayes ratio provides no meaningful support. The Bayes factor, in these cases, reflects the role of CO as a bulk background gas rather than the detectability of its 4.7 μm absorption feature.

Figure 3.10: Bayes factor comparison for models including CO (\mathcal{M}_1) versus models without CO (\mathcal{M}_2), across atmospheric scenarios and S/N. Colors indicate $\log_{10} K$, while cell labels mark the corresponding Jeffreys category.

3.3.2 Impact on Other Molecules

Having now determined that for our more complex models the presence of CO cannot be verified, we move to testing the difference in retrieval performance when including or excluding the 4–6 μm range, to quantify if and how much those bands impact the quality of the retrievals. To do so we compare the results in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 with a new set of retrievals run under the same exact conditions, but only considering the 6–18.5 μm wavelength range. For each model and S/N we compute a prior-normalized RMSE for every parameter θ (Equation (2.4)). For log-Gaussian we use 5σ as W_{prior} , and for the surface temperature T_0 we use the width propagated from the P-T profile coefficient priors. For each parameter we report the relative RMSE percentage improvement of the 4–18.5 μm over the 6–18.5 μm case calculated as

$$\text{Improvement}(\theta) [\%] = 100 \times \frac{\text{RMSE}^{6-18.5}(\theta) - \text{RMSE}^{4-18.5}(\theta)}{\text{RMSE}^{4-18.5}(\theta)}. \quad (3.2)$$

Positive values mean that excluding the 4–6 μm range increases the RMSE, which indicates a worse retrieval performance: so 4–18.5 μm is better. Negative values mean the opposite. We can visualize this compactly in Figure 3.11, which shows the relative RMSE percentage improvement for each parameter, for each model, for each S/N. Bar heights encode the relative improvement in log scale, and values are capped at $\pm 100\%$ for clarity. Bars above the baseline indicate a benefit from the 4–6 μm range. The final column summarizes the mean improvement over all displayed parameters for that model and S/N, giving us a simple metric to evaluate the overall difference between the two wavelength ranges.

We find that for CO, all scenarios and S/N levels favor the full 4–18.5 μm range. This result is expected given the strong CO fundamental near 4.7 μm and confirms the internal consistency of our analysis.

When considering the average performance across parameters, the *Null*, *Null Dry*, and *Paradise* models show slightly better retrieval metrics when restricted to 6–18.5 μm , whereas the *Cyanosulfidic Dry* model favors the full 4–18.5 μm range and the *Cyanosulfidic* model exhibits an S/N-dependent behavior. In all models except *Cyanosulfidic*, the average improvement is minor. In the *Cyanosulfidic* scenario, there is a strong dependence on S/N: the S/N = 10 case favors the full range, while S/N = 20 favors the reduced 6–18.5 μm range. These trends appear to be driven primarily by the P_0 and T_0 parameters, with no significant differences observed in the retrieved molecular abundances. Further analysis is needed to investigate the origin of these variations.

The apparent improvement when excluding the 4–6 μm region should not be interpreted as evidence that reduced spectral coverage is preferable. Rather, it indicates that this wavelength interval contributes little additional constraining power for these specific scenarios.

3.3.3 Implications for LIFE

Within the scope of our analysis, the results are consistent with [Konrad et al. \(2024\)](#): adding the 4–6 μm segment does not significantly improve constraints or precision on the quantities of interest. We also find no conclusive evidence that CO can be detected

Figure 3.11: Relative change in RMSE when the 4–6 μm range is included. Each row corresponds to a model and each column to a parameter. For each parameter, three bars ($S/N = 10, 20, 50$) show the percentage improvement. Bars extend upward for positive values (4–18.5 μm better) and downward for negative values (6–18.5 μm better). Heights use a logarithmic mapping and are capped at $\pm 100\%$; the right-hand scale marks 1, 10, and 100%. The final column reports the average improvement across parameters for each model and S/N .

from the 4.7 μm band in these scenarios. Consequently, the 4–6 μm range appears non-essential for the science cases considered here, suggesting that a LIFE configuration focusing on 6–18.5 μm could simplify engineering with little to no loss in performance for our targets. A shorter long-wavelength cutoff (e.g., 6–16.5 μm) might offer further simplifications, but we have not tested that option here and leave it as open future work.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

4.1 Conclusion

In this work we have investigated the capability of the LIFE mission to retrieve the physical properties and atmospheric abundances of terrestrial exoplanets, with a focus on early-Earth analogs. Using synthetic spectra generated for five atmospheric scenarios, *Null*, *Null Dry*, *Cyanosulfidic*, *Cyanosulfidic Dry*, and *Prebiotic Paradise*, we carried out Bayesian retrievals at three noise levels ($S/N = 10, 20, 50$) and assessed their performance using Bayes factors, posterior distributions, and RMSE metric.

In all cases the spectrum posterior reproduced the input spectra within the simulated noise, demonstrating that the retrieval framework correctly captures the global features of the flux. However, the vertical thermal structure is only moderately constrained: the retrieved P-T profiles show good agreement up to the infrared photosphere, but the constraints loosen above approximately 10^{-2} bar and are often biased near the surface at low S/N. This illustrates both the strength and the limitations of the current P-T parametrization.

The molecular retrievals reveal distinct behaviors across the different atmospheric scenarios. In the *Null* and *Null Dry* cases, which represent the simplest atmospheres, most molecules remain unconstrained. The weak infrared signatures of H_2 , N_2 , and CO do not allow for any meaningful retrieval, while CO_2 is detected but systematically overestimated. This bias is linked to degeneracies between planetary mass, gravity, and molecular abundances, which become particularly evident in atmospheres with limited chemical complexity. The dry case shows slightly improved surface constraints, but does not fundamentally alter the molecular retrieval picture. These patterns for H_2 , N_2 , CO, and CO_2 emerge across all models, albeit at different strengths.

In the *Cyanosulfidic* and *Cyanosulfidic Dry* scenarios, the addition of sulfur species changes the retrieval landscape. SO_2 emerges as a robustly constrained molecule, with abundances consistently recovered across all S/N. H_2S , in contrast, is retrieved only as an upper limit, with constraints that remain broad even at high S/N. The presence of SO_2 also affects the continuum in the 8–10 μm region, reducing the accuracy with which surface properties can be probed. The dry version again improves surface constraints but does not significantly enhance the retrieval of sulfur species.

The *Paradise* scenario, with its higher chemical complexity, reveals the greatest diversity of outcomes. CH_4 is very well constrained at all S/N levels, and C_2H_2 becomes increasingly well constrained as S/N improves, showing that these hydrocarbons are accessible to LIFE under favorable conditions. HCN also becomes measurable, though with sensitivity-limited posteriors at all S/N. H_2S remains difficult to retrieve, except at the highest S/N. Despite its distinct band at 5.3 μm , NO remains unconstrained in all cases, suggesting that overlap with stronger absorbers such as H_2O and CO_2 effectively masks its signal.

Overall, the molecular retrievals paint a heterogeneous picture. Robust detections are possible for species with strong, isolated features (e.g., SO_2 , CH_4 , CO_2), partial constraints arise for others (e.g., H_2S , HCN), and some remain beyond reach under the

assumed conditions (e.g., NO, N₂, H₂, CO). The recurring overestimation of CO₂ illustrates how degeneracies between thermal structure, water content, and bulk parameters strongly shape retrieval outcomes. Together, these results underscore both the diagnostic potential of MIR emission spectroscopy and the importance of carefully addressing degeneracies and spectral overlaps when interpreting exoplanet atmospheres.

Water vapor plays a particularly central role. In non-dry cases, vertical profiles are retrieved with good fidelity in the lower atmosphere, but the upper-atmosphere water content is systematically underestimated due to the monotonic drying scheme. This structural mismatch propagates into biases in planetary mass and other parameters, reinforcing the conclusion that water strongly couples to both the thermal structure and the pressure scale.

Comparing dry and non-dry cases reveals broadly similar retrieval behavior, but with notable differences. The dry models more accurately recover surface conditions, as the continuum is less obscured by water opacity. They also show improved constraints on some atmospheric species, which benefit from reduced interference by water features. This highlights the dual role of H₂O: essential as a pressure anchor in non-dry cases, but also a source of degeneracies and biases when not well represented.

In general, already at S/N 10 the retrievals perform well for all models. Only for H₂S and C₂H₂ in the *Paradise* case do we see significant improvements with S/N.

A key practical question addressed in this thesis concerns the role of the 4–6 μm spectral range. Our results show that this interval adds little constraining power for the considered scenarios. Bayes factors indicate strong support for CO detection only in the simplest *Null Dry* case and *Null* at high S/N, while in more complex atmospheres there is virtually no difference. In all cases CO is unconstrained, so it behaves mainly as a background gas rather than being detected through its 4.7 μm band. The RMSE further confirms that excluding the 4–6 μm region does not have a clear negative impact on the retrievals, supporting the conclusion that focusing on the 6–18.5 μm range is sufficient for these early-Earth analogs. This finding has direct implications for instrument design, suggesting that relaxing the short-wavelength coverage could simplify the engineering complexity while maintaining scientific standards.

Additional validation tests strengthen the robustness of these conclusions. In Appendix B we showed that extending the molecular set does not induce spurious detections: absent species are generally unconstrained or constrained to upper limits, with some exceptions. In Appendix C we demonstrated that fixing the P-T profile and surface pressure to their true values strongly improves radius constraints across all models. Mass behaves differently in dry and non-dry scenarios: it tightens in the latter due to vertical water structure but broadens in the former, where pressure anchoring is weak. Abundance posteriors, especially for CO₂, degrade when the fixed thermal structure is inconsistent with the retrieved water profile, illustrating the strong role of H₂O in shaping degeneracies.

Taken together, these results provide a consistent and detailed picture of the strengths and limitations of MIR emission spectroscopy for terrestrial exoplanets. LIFE will be capable of constraining key molecules, surface conditions, and bulk parameters under realistic noise assumptions, but degeneracies involving water, CO₂, and the thermal structure require careful modeling. The retrieval framework has demonstrated robustness against spurious detections, while also introducing systematic biases for some

specific cases. These insights form a solid basis for guiding both future methodological developments and design decisions for LIFE.

4.2 Outlook

While the results presented here demonstrate the capability of LIFE to characterize early Earth-like atmospheres, they also reveal important limitations and point toward several promising directions for future work.

The first priority is to improve the physical realism of the atmospheric parametrizations. The current monotonic drying scheme for H₂O systematically underestimates the upper-atmosphere water content. The focus should therefore be to allow for more flexible vertical profiles, in order to capture effects that are expected in real atmospheres. Similarly, the fourth-degree polynomial currently used for the P-T structure provides only limited flexibility. More robust parametrizations would help mitigate systematic biases and reduce degeneracies between temperature gradients and other retrieved parameters.

Another promising avenue is to extend the broad molecular set validation presented in Appendix B, exploring larger and more chemically diverse molecular inventories to further test the robustness of retrieval frameworks against incomplete or biased assumptions.

From a methodological standpoint, Bayesian evidence has proven useful for model selection, but future work should incorporate additional metrics such as the Deviance Information Criterion (DIC) and the Watanabe-Akaike Information Criterion (WAIC), as well as posterior predictive checks. These complementary diagnostics would strengthen the statistical robustness of retrieval comparisons and help identify overfitting or prior-driven results.

In terms of wavelength coverage, our analysis strongly suggests that the 4–6 μm region contributes little to retrieval performance for early-Earth analogs. A natural next step is to explore this trade-off more systematically, considering not only alternative wavelength cutoffs (such as 6–16.5 μm), but also the impact of varying spectral resolution. Such studies will help define the optimal balance between scientific return and engineering feasibility.

It should also be noted that the noise model implemented in LIFEsim and adopted in this work does not include instrumental noise sources. The simulated noisy spectra therefore represent an idealized photon-limited case and do not fully capture LIFE’s expected observational noise characteristics. Incorporating more realistic instrument models in future analyses will be essential to fully assess LIFE’s retrieval capabilities under operational conditions.

Finally, future work should address potential biases introduced by inconsistencies between opacity datasets, and make sure that retrieval results reflect atmospheric physics rather than database differences.

In summary, this thesis has shown that LIFE can robustly constrain key aspects of early Earth-like terrestrial exoplanets, but it has also highlighted where retrievals are most vulnerable to degeneracies and model assumptions. Addressing these challenges will require improvements in parametrizations and statistical methods, along with better defined assumptions about observational noise, spectral resolution, and

instrument performance. Together, these steps will provide a solid basis upon which we can advance retrieval methodologies and refine observational strategies that will ultimately strengthen the scientific return of LIFE and ensure that its measurements can be interpreted with confidence.

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Prof. Quanz, who gave me the opportunity to work in his group and always took time out of his busy schedule to provide guidance. Thank you, Sascha, for making sure I was doing well throughout these months, for your words of encouragement, and for always treating me with kindness and genuine interest, which made working with you not only a privilege, but a real pleasure.

I am also very grateful to the whole group for welcoming me so warmly and making this period such a bright chapter in my studies. Your genuine care and interest in my work gave it greater meaning and made me feel part of a common goal. In particular, I would like to thank Dibya, Felix, Janina, Zach, and Sean, who more than anyone else had to carry the weight of my many questions. My appreciation also goes to my fellow master's students, for the camaraderie and encouragement we shared throughout this journey.

I owe special thanks to Alastair and Paul for generously providing the input spectra used in this thesis and for their valuable advice during the early stages of my work.

I am deeply grateful to my friends, who patiently listened to me talk about this project for far more hours than they probably wished for. A particular mention goes to Micha, who, unbeknownst to him, has been a constant source of support and perspective.

Finally, I would like to thank my family for their unwavering encouragement and support. To my mother Monica, thank you for always reminding me of what truly matters, and of the purpose behind it all. To my father Lorenzo, thank you for showing me the kind of person I aspire to be. To my wonderful sister Penelope, thank you for your affectionate care and for always believing in me. To my uncle Maurizio, thank you for always being there when I need you, no matter what.

And to my amazing girlfriend Sara: thank you for being by my side through both the struggles and the triumphs of this thesis. Your support made the difficult moments lighter and the good moments brighter. Every step of this journey was easier, and every success more meaningful, because you were there.

Bibliography

Alduchov O. A. and Eskridge R. E. (1996)

Improved Magnus Form Approximation of Saturation Vapor Pressure.

Alei E., Konrad B. S., Angerhausen D., et al. (2022)

Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE) - V. Diagnostic potential of a mid-infrared space interferometer for studying Earth analogs

DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202243760](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202243760).

Alei E., Quanz S. P., Konrad B. S., et al. (2024)

Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE): XIII. The Value of Combining Thermal Emission and Reflected Light for the Characterization of Earth Twins

DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202450320](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202450320).

Amyay B., Fayt A., Herman M., et al. (2016)

Vibration-rotation spectroscopic database on acetylene, $X^{\sim} 1\Sigma_g^+$ ($^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$)

DOI: [10.1063/1.4947297](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4947297).

Azzam Ala'a A. A., Tennyson Jonathan, Yurchenko Sergei N., et al. (2016)

ExoMol molecular line lists - XVI. The rotation-vibration spectrum of hot H_2S

DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw1133](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw1133).

Barber R. J., Strange J. K., Hill C., et al. (2014)

ExoMol line lists - III. An improved hot rotation-vibration line list for HCN and HNC

DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stt2011](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt2011).

Bolcar M. R., Zhao F., Scowen P., et al. (2025)

The Habitable Worlds Observatory technology development plan

DOI: [10.1117/12.3065725](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3065725).

Bracewell R. N. (1978)

Detecting nonsolar planets by spinning infrared interferometer

DOI: [10.1038/274780a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/274780a0).

Buchner J., Georgakakis A., Nandra K., et al. (2014)

X-ray spectral modelling of the AGN obscuring region in the CDFS: Bayesian model selection and catalogue

DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201322971](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322971).

- Chen J. and Kipping D. (2016)
Probabilistic Forecasting of the Masses And Radii of Other Worlds
DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/17](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/17).
- Chubb Katy L., Tennyson Jonathan, and Yurchenko Sergei N. (2020)
ExoMol molecular line lists - XXXVII. Spectra of acetylene
DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa229](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa229).
- Claringbold A. B., Rimmer P. B., Rugheimer S., et al. (2023)
Prebiosignature Molecules Can Be Detected in Temperate Exoplanet Atmospheres with JWST
DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/acdacc](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/acdacc).
- Conway Eamon K., Gordon Iouli E., Tennyson Jonathan, et al. (2020)
A semi-empirical potential energy surface and line list for H₂¹⁶O extending into the near-ultraviolet
DOI: [10.5194/acp-20-10015-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-10015-2020).
- Dannert F. A., Ottiger M., Quanz S. P., et al. (2022)
Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE) - II. Signal simulation, signal extraction, and fundamental exoplanet parameters from single-epoch observations
DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202141958](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141958).
- Gaudi B. S., Seager S., Mennesson B., et al. (2020)
The Habitable Exoplanet Observatory (HabEx) Mission Concept Study Final Report
DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2001.06683](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2001.06683).
- Glauser A. M., Quanz S. P., Hansen J., et al. (2024)
The Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE): a space mission for mid-infrared nulling interferometry
DOI: [10.1117/12.3019090](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3019090).
- Goff J. A. (1957)
Saturation pressure of water on the new Kelvin temperature scale.
- Goff J. A. and Gratch S. (1946)
Low-pressure properties of water from -160 to 212 °F.
- Gordon I. E., Rothman L. S., Hargreaves R. J., et al. (2022)
The HITRAN2020 molecular spectroscopic database
DOI: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.107949](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.107949).
- Hargreaves Robert J., Gordon Iouli E., Rey Michael, et al. (2020)
An Accurate, Extensive, and Practical Line List of Methane for the HITEMP Database
DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/ab7a1a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ab7a1a).

- Jeffreys H. (1998)
Theory of Probability
DOI: [10.1093/oso/9780198503682.002.0001](https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198503682.002.0001).
- Kasting J. F. (1990)
Bolide impacts and the oxidation state of carbon in the Earth's early atmosphere
DOI: [10.1007/BF01808105](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01808105).
- Konrad B. S., Alei E., Quanz S. P., et al. (2022)
Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE) - III. Spectral resolution, wavelength range, and sensitivity requirements based on atmospheric retrieval analyses of an exo-Earth
DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202141964](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141964).
- Konrad B. S., Quanz S. P., Alei E., et al. (2024)
Pursuing Truth: Improving Retrievals on Mid-infrared Exo-Earth Spectra with Physically Motivated Water Abundance Profiles and Cloud Models
DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ad74f7](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ad74f7).
- Li Gang, Gordon Iouli E., Rothman Laurence S., et al. (2015)
Rovibrational line lists for nine isotopologues of the CO molecule in the $X^1\Sigma^+$ ground electronic state
DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/216/1/15](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/216/1/15).
- Madhusudhan N. (2019)
Exoplanetary Atmospheres: Key Insights, Challenges and Prospects
DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-081817-051846](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-081817-051846).
- Mayor M. and Queloz D. (1995)
A Jupiter-mass companion to a solar-type star
DOI: [10.1038/378355a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/378355a0).
- Mollière P., Wardenier J. P., Boekel R. van, et al. (2019)
petitRADTRANS: a Python radiative transfer package for exoplanet characterization and retrieval
DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201935470](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935470).
- Padovani P. and Cirasuolo M. (2023)
The Extremely Large Telescope
DOI: [10.1080/00107514.2023.2266921](https://doi.org/10.1080/00107514.2023.2266921).
- Patel B. H., Percivalle C., Ritson D. J., et al. (2015)
Common origins of RNA, protein and lipid precursors in a cyanosulfidic protometabolism
DOI: [10.1038/nchem.2202](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.2202).

- Pearce B. K. D., Molaverdikhani K., Pudritz R. E., et al. (2022)
Toward RNA Life on Early Earth: From Atmospheric HCN to Biomolecule Production in Warm Little Ponds
DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac47a1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac47a1).
- Peterson B. M., Fischer D., and LUVOIR Science and Technology Definition Team (2017)
The Large Ultraviolet/Optical/Infrared Surveyor (LUVOIR).
- Pica-Ciamarra L., Madhusudhan N., Cooke G. J., et al. (2025)
A Systematic Search for Trace Molecules in Exoplanet K2-18 b
DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2505.10539](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.10539).
- Quanz S. P., Ottiger M., Fontanet E., et al. (2022)
Large Interferometer For Exoplanets (LIFE): I. Improved exoplanet detection yield estimates for a large mid-infrared space-interferometer mission
DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202140366](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202140366).
- Richard C., Gordon I. E., Rothman L. S., et al. (2012)
New section of the HITRAN database: Collision-induced absorption (CIA)
DOI: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2011.11.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2011.11.004).
- Rimmer P. B. and Rugheimer S. (2019)
Hydrogen cyanide in nitrogen-rich atmospheres of rocky exoplanets
DOI: [10.1016/j.icarus.2019.02.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2019.02.020).
- Rothman L. S., Gordon I. E., Barber R. J., et al. (2010)
HITEMP, the high-temperature molecular spectroscopic database
DOI: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2010.05.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2010.05.001).
- Rugheimer S. and Kaltenegger L. (2018)
Spectra of Earth-like Planets through Geological Evolution around FGKM Stars
DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aaa47a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aaa47a).
- Seager S., Welbanks L., Ellerbroek L., et al. (2025)
Prospects for detecting signs of life on exoplanets in the JWST era
DOI: [10.1073/pnas.2416188122](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2416188122).
- Stevenson K. B., Lustig-Yaeger J., May E. M., et al. (2025)
K2-18b Does Not Meet The Standards of Evidence For Life
DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2508.05961](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2508.05961).
- Tashkun S. A., Perevalov V. I., Gamache R. R., et al. (2019)
CDSD-296, high-resolution carbon dioxide spectroscopic databank: An update
DOI: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2019.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2019.03.001).

- Tennyson Jonathan, Yurchenko Sergei N., Al-Refaie Ahmed F., et al. (2016)
The ExoMol database: Molecular line lists for exoplanet and other hot atmospheres
DOI: [10.1016/j.jms.2016.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jms.2016.05.002).
- Underwood Daniel S., Tennyson Jonathan, Yurchenko Sergei N., et al. (2016)
ExoMol molecular line lists - XIV. The rotation-vibration spectrum of hot SO₂
DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw849](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw849).
- Wang Y., Tian F., Li T., et al. (2016)
On the detection of carbon monoxide as an anti-biosignature in exoplanetary atmospheres
DOI: [10.1016/j.icarus.2015.11.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2015.11.010).
- Welbanks Luis, Nixon Matthew C., McGill Peter, et al. (2025)
The Challenges of Detecting Gases in Exoplanet Atmospheres
DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2504.21788](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.21788).
- Wong Andy, Yurchenko Sergei N., Bernath Peter, et al. (2017)
ExoMol line list - XXI. Nitric Oxide (NO)
DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx1211](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx1211).
- Yurchenko S. N., Amundsen D. S., Tennyson J., et al. (2017)
A hybrid line list for CH₄ and hot methane continuum
DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201731026](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201731026).
- Yurchenko S. N., Mellor Thomas M., Freedman Richard S., et al. (2020)
ExoMol line lists - XXXIX. Ro-vibrational molecular line list for CO₂
DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa1874](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa1874).
- Zahnle K. J., Gacesa M., and Catling D. C. (2019)
Strange messenger: A new history of hydrogen on Earth, as told by Xenon
DOI: [10.1016/j.gca.2018.09.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2018.09.017).

A Supplementary Data from the Retrievals

This appendix reports parameter summaries for each atmospheric scenario. Each table lists parameters by row; columns give the retrieved values at S/N = 10, 20, and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), followed by the truth. All molecular abundances are in VMR, and other units are indicated in the row labels. Corner plots for all scenarios (S/N = 10, 20, 50) are available at [this link](#).

Parameter	S/N = 10	S/N = 20	S/N = 50	Truth
a_4	4.9 $^{+4.1}_{-3.1}$	3.4 $^{+2.8}_{-2.0}$	2.5 $^{+1.2}_{-1.1}$	-
a_3	38.7 $^{+31.0}_{-20.7}$	27.8 $^{+20.9}_{-14.1}$	21.6 $^{+9.2}_{-8.0}$	-
a_2	108.8 $^{+78.9}_{-50.8}$	86.5 $^{+55.9}_{-35.1}$	72.4 $^{+26.2}_{-20.2}$	-
a_1	141.0 $^{+89.4}_{-61.0}$	130.3 $^{+64.5}_{-44.0}$	119.1 $^{+35.4}_{-24.7}$	-
a_0	282.3 $^{+40.3}_{-28.2}$	287.6 $^{+31.6}_{-24.5}$	288.1 $^{+20.5}_{-15.5}$	-
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	0.03 $^{+0.28}_{-0.23}$	-0.02 $^{+0.25}_{-0.19}$	-0.01 $^{+0.15}_{-0.16}$	0.00
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	0.96 $^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	0.97 $^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$	0.982 $^{+0.018}_{-0.019}$	1.00
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	-0.18 $^{+0.30}_{-0.30}$	-0.30 $^{+0.28}_{-0.27}$	-0.51 $^{+0.19}_{-0.17}$	0.00
$\log_{10}(\text{N}_2)$	-5.2 $^{+3.1}_{-2.9}$	-5.2 $^{+3.2}_{-3.1}$	-5.1 $^{+3.1}_{-3.2}$	-0.2
$\log_{10}(\text{CO}_2)$	-0.6 $^{+0.4}_{-0.5}$	-0.6 $^{+0.4}_{-0.5}$	-0.8 $^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	-0.7
$\log_{10}(\text{CO})$	-5.1 $^{+3.2}_{-3.2}$	-5.0 $^{+3.1}_{-3.2}$	-4.7 $^{+3.0}_{-3.4}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2)$	-5.3 $^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	-5.2 $^{+3.2}_{-3.0}$	-5.2 $^{+3.2}_{-3.1}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-1.7 $^{+1.1}_{-1.2}$	-1.4 $^{+0.9}_{-1.0}$	-1.2 $^{+0.8}_{-0.8}$	-
$\log_{10}(\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$	-2.3 $^{+1.5}_{-1.6}$	-1.9 $^{+1.3}_{-1.7}$	-1.0 $^{+0.7}_{-1.1}$	-
$\log_{10}(\text{HCN})$	-4.5 $^{+1.6}_{-3.2}$	-3.9 $^{+1.2}_{-3.5}$	-4.5 $^{+0.9}_{-2.5}$	-4.0
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{S})$	-6.4 $^{+2.1}_{-2.2}$	-6.3 $^{+2.0}_{-2.3}$	-4.4 $^{+0.5}_{-1.2}$	-4.0
$\log_{10}(\text{NO})$	-5.0 $^{+2.9}_{-3.2}$	-5.2 $^{+3.1}_{-3.1}$	-5.0 $^{+3.0}_{-3.2}$	-4.0
$\log_{10}(\text{CH}_4)$	-3.9 $^{+0.6}_{-0.8}$	-3.8 $^{+0.4}_{-0.5}$	-4.3 $^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	-4.0
$\log_{10}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2)$	-5.1 $^{+1.5}_{-2.7}$	-4.5 $^{+0.8}_{-2.6}$	-4.1 $^{+0.3}_{-0.4}$	-4.0

Table A.1: Retrieved parameter summary for the *Prebiotic Paradise* model at S/N = 10, 20, and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), and the true value.

Parameter	S/N = 10	S/N = 20	S/N = 50	Truth
a_4	5.0 $^{+4.2}_{-3.0}$	3.4 $^{+2.9}_{-2.2}$	3.1 $^{+1.4}_{-1.3}$	-
a_3	40.3 $^{+32.1}_{-20.6}$	28.8 $^{+21.9}_{-15.1}$	28.2 $^{+11.4}_{-10.0}$	-
a_2	116.3 $^{+84.7}_{-48.5}$	91.6 $^{+60.8}_{-36.0}$	95.5 $^{+33.3}_{-27.3}$	-
a_1	159.2 $^{+87.4}_{-60.2}$	139.7 $^{+72.1}_{-42.7}$	153.9 $^{+45.1}_{-33.5}$	-
a_0	296.1 $^{+39.3}_{-27.4}$	296.1 $^{+35.7}_{-24.0}$	308.3 $^{+24.9}_{-19.3}$	-
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	-0.05 $^{+0.24}_{-0.19}$	-0.07 $^{+0.21}_{-0.20}$	-0.17 $^{+0.14}_{-0.14}$	0.00
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	0.94 $^{+0.05}_{-0.06}$	0.97 $^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$	0.986 $^{+0.018}_{-0.018}$	1.00
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	-0.19 $^{+0.26}_{-0.26}$	-0.27 $^{+0.27}_{-0.26}$	-0.37 $^{+0.20}_{-0.19}$	0.00
$\log_{10}(\text{N}_2)$	-5.2 $^{+2.9}_{-2.9}$	-5.1 $^{+3.1}_{-3.2}$	-5.3 $^{+3.3}_{-3.1}$	-0.2
$\log_{10}(\text{CO}_2)$	-0.56 $^{+0.30}_{-0.36}$	-0.49 $^{+0.23}_{-0.29}$	-0.39 $^{+0.16}_{-0.17}$	-0.70
$\log_{10}(\text{CO})$	-5.0 $^{+2.9}_{-2.8}$	-5.1 $^{+3.1}_{-3.1}$	-4.7 $^{+3.0}_{-3.5}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2)$	-5.3 $^{+3.2}_{-2.9}$	-5.3 $^{+3.2}_{-3.0}$	-5.3 $^{+3.2}_{-3.1}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-1.4 $^{+0.9}_{-0.9}$	-1.2 $^{+0.8}_{-0.9}$	-1.1 $^{+0.7}_{-0.8}$	-
$\log_{10}(\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$	-2.4 $^{+1.5}_{-1.5}$	-1.8 $^{+1.2}_{-1.6}$	-1.2 $^{+0.7}_{-1.0}$	-

Table A.2: Retrieved parameter summary for the *Null* model at $S/N = 10, 20,$ and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), and the true value.

Parameter	S/N = 10	S/N = 20	S/N = 50	Truth
a_4	4.6 $^{+4.3}_{-3.0}$	3.6 $^{+3.1}_{-2.2}$	3.3 $^{+1.4}_{-1.3}$	-
a_3	37.0 $^{+31.8}_{-20.0}$	30.5 $^{+24.9}_{-15.2}$	29.2 $^{+11.4}_{-9.9}$	-
a_2	107.8 $^{+83.5}_{-50.0}$	96.9 $^{+67.4}_{-39.1}$	98.2 $^{+32.7}_{-26.7}$	-
a_1	145.3 $^{+99.2}_{-59.1}$	146.0 $^{+83.0}_{-45.5}$	156.0 $^{+43.5}_{-34.0}$	-
a_0	289.9 $^{+45.2}_{-29.7}$	297.2 $^{+42.3}_{-24.5}$	308.2 $^{+23.9}_{-19.4}$	-
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	-0.02 $^{+0.28}_{-0.24}$	-0.10 $^{+0.21}_{-0.21}$	-0.17 $^{+0.14}_{-0.13}$	0.00
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	0.96 $^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	0.98 $^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	0.992 $^{+0.017}_{-0.017}$	1.00
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	-0.17 $^{+0.32}_{-0.31}$	-0.26 $^{+0.30}_{-0.29}$	-0.34 $^{+0.25}_{-0.22}$	0.00
$\log_{10}(\text{N}_2)$	-5.3 $^{+3.2}_{-3.1}$	-5.2 $^{+3.0}_{-3.1}$	-5.4 $^{+3.4}_{-3.0}$	-0.2
$\log_{10}(\text{CO}_2)$	-0.5 $^{+0.3}_{-0.5}$	-0.38 $^{+0.25}_{-0.37}$	-0.30 $^{+0.20}_{-0.28}$	-0.7
$\log_{10}(\text{CO})$	-5.1 $^{+3.2}_{-3.2}$	-5.1 $^{+3.1}_{-3.1}$	-4.6 $^{+3.0}_{-3.5}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2)$	-5.3 $^{+3.2}_{-3.0}$	-5.4 $^{+3.2}_{-2.9}$	-5.6 $^{+3.3}_{-3.0}$	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-7.2 $^{+1.5}_{-1.8}$	-6.6 $^{+0.9}_{-1.9}$	-5.85 $^{+0.32}_{-0.40}$	-6.0

Table A.3: Retrieved parameter summary for the *Null Dry* model at $S/N = 10, 20,$ and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), and the true value.

Parameter	S/N = 10	S/N = 20	S/N = 50	Truth
a_4	4.0 ^{+4.4} _{-2.7}	3.0 ^{+2.9} _{-2.1}	2.6 ^{+1.4} _{-1.2}	-
a_3	31.8 ^{+32.3} _{-18.9}	25.5 ^{+22.2} _{-15.1}	23.1 ^{+10.7} _{-8.9}	-
a_2	92.4 ^{+79.7} _{-47.1}	82.5 ^{+55.8} _{-37.9}	80.3 ^{+29.6} _{-23.0}	-
a_1	127.6 ^{+84.2} _{-50.2}	127.9 ^{+63.2} _{-43.4}	133.1 ^{+38.1} _{-26.2}	-
a_0	287.9 ^{+36.9} _{-25.3}	291.4 ^{+30.2} _{-22.5}	297.7 ^{+21.4} _{-15.4}	-
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	0.07 ^{+0.34} _{-0.25}	0.00 ^{+0.29} _{-0.21}	-0.08 ^{+0.14} _{-0.14}	0.00
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	0.93 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	0.96 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	0.970 ^{+0.021} _{-0.020}	1.00
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	-0.17 ^{+0.30} _{-0.28}	-0.27 ^{+0.26} _{-0.24}	-0.37 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	0.00
$\log_{10}(\text{N}_2)$	-5.2 ^{+3.1} _{-3.0}	-5.1 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-5.1 ^{+3.3} _{-3.3}	-0.2
$\log_{10}(\text{CO}_2)$	-0.6 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	-0.59 ^{+0.30} _{-0.33}	-0.54 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	-0.7
$\log_{10}(\text{CO})$	-5.3 ^{+3.1} _{-3.0}	-5.2 ^{+3.3} _{-3.1}	-4.6 ^{+3.0} _{-3.6}	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2)$	-5.3 ^{+3.2} _{-3.0}	-5.1 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-5.3 ^{+3.2} _{-3.2}	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-1.4 ^{+0.9} _{-1.0}	-1.2 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}	-1.1 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	-
$\log_{10}(\text{HCN})$	-6.4 ^{+2.1} _{-2.2}	-6.6 ^{+1.9} _{-2.2}	-5.9 ^{+1.2} _{-2.6}	-5.0
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{S})$	-7.1 ^{+2.0} _{-1.9}	-7.3 ^{+1.8} _{-1.7}	-7.6 ^{+1.6} _{-1.6}	-5.0
$\log_{10}(\text{SO}_2)$	-4.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	-4.93 ^{+0.27} _{-0.28}	-4.95 ^{+0.15} _{-0.15}	-5.0
$\log_{10}(\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$	-2.4 ^{+1.5} _{-1.6}	-1.8 ^{+1.2} _{-1.7}	-1.1 ^{+0.7} _{-1.0}	-

Table A.4: Retrieved parameter summary for the *Cyanosulfidic* model at $S/N = 10, 20,$ and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), and the true value.

Parameter	S/N = 10	S/N = 20	S/N = 50	Truth
a_4	4.8 ^{+4.0} _{-3.3}	3.5 ^{+2.9} _{-2.1}	2.9 ^{+1.4} _{-1.3}	-
a_3	37.9 ^{+30.5} _{-21.8}	29.1 ^{+22.6} _{-14.8}	26.1 ^{+10.8} _{-9.2}	-
a_2	106.5 ^{+79.9} _{-47.5}	91.4 ^{+63.8} _{-35.7}	87.5 ^{+30.7} _{-22.9}	-
a_1	145.1 ^{+86.8} _{-58.0}	138.8 ^{+74.6} _{-44.0}	140.8 ^{+39.8} _{-26.8}	-
a_0	287.8 ^{+38.4} _{-29.5}	290.9 ^{+36.0} _{-24.3}	297.5 ^{+22.2} _{-15.5}	-
$\log_{10}(P_0 [\text{bar}])$	-0.03 ^{+0.26} _{-0.20}	-0.07 ^{+0.22} _{-0.20}	-0.11 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	0.00
$R_{\text{pl}} [R_{\oplus}]$	0.97 ^{+0.07} _{-0.06}	0.99 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	0.996 ^{+0.020} _{-0.020}	1.00
$\log_{10}(M_{\text{pl}} [M_{\oplus}])$	-0.11 ^{+0.34} _{-0.30}	-0.19 ^{+0.32} _{-0.29}	-0.24 ^{+0.24} _{-0.25}	0.00
$\log_{10}(\text{N}_2)$	-5.3 ^{+3.2} _{-3.2}	-5.2 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-5.3 ^{+3.3} _{-3.1}	-0.2
$\log_{10}(\text{CO}_2)$	-0.48 ^{+0.31} _{-0.47}	-0.41 ^{+0.27} _{-0.40}	-0.33 ^{+0.22} _{-0.32}	-0.70
$\log_{10}(\text{CO})$	-5.1 ^{+3.3} _{-3.1}	-5.0 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-4.3 ^{+2.8} _{-3.7}	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2)$	-5.2 ^{+3.2} _{-3.1}	-5.1 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-5.3 ^{+3.1} _{-3.2}	-1.3
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-6.9 ^{+1.5} _{-2.0}	-6.8 ^{+1.2} _{-2.0}	-6.0 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	-6.0
$\log_{10}(\text{HCN})$	-6.2 ^{+1.5} _{-2.4}	-5.2 ^{+0.5} _{-0.9}	-4.94 ^{+0.27} _{-0.32}	-5.0
$\log_{10}(\text{H}_2\text{S})$	-7.1 ^{+1.8} _{-1.9}	-7.3 ^{+1.8} _{-1.8}	-6.7 ^{+1.6} _{-2.2}	-5.0
$\log_{10}(\text{SO}_2)$	-4.9 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	-4.85 ^{+0.25} _{-0.34}	-4.80 ^{+0.22} _{-0.29}	-5.0

Table A.5: Retrieved parameter summary for the *Cyanosulfidic Dry* model at $S/N = 10, 20,$ and 50 (median with 68 % credible interval), and the true value.

B Validation of the Framework with a Broader Molecular Set

The recent debate surrounding *K2-18b* has highlighted how retrieval outcomes can depend strongly on the set of molecules included in a model. Initial analyses reported a possible detection of dimethyl sulfide (DMS) and dimethyl disulfide (DMDS), but later studies showed that the statistical preference for these species disappeared when a broader set of molecules was considered (Stevenson et al. 2025; Welbanks et al. 2025). In that case, the change in Bayesian evidence reflected that other molecular combinations could explain the data equally well or better, emphasizing the sensitivity of retrieval results to the completeness of the prior space. In this context, Pica-Ciamarra et al. (2025) conducted a wide-ranging, agnostic retrieval over 650 candidate molecules for *K2-18b*, illustrating how apparently compelling spectral features can disappear under more comprehensive and conservative models.

Motivated by these lessons, we performed a validation test of PyRetLIFE aimed at assessing its behavior when the molecular set is deliberately extended beyond the true atmospheric composition. Specifically, we test whether the framework correctly assigns negligible abundances to molecules that are not present in the input spectra, rather than misinterpreting random noise or spectral degeneracies as evidence for their presence. This experiment therefore evaluates the robustness of the retrievals with respect to the completeness of the prior space.

The validation was carried out at $S/N = 50$, where the data are most informative and any tendency to assign spurious abundances would be most apparent. Demonstrating that absent molecules remain unconstrained or consistent with very low abundances under these conditions provides confidence that the framework is robust and does not introduce false positive detections.

We therefore included the following molecules as free parameters in all retrieval models: N_2 , CO_2 , CO , H_2 , H_2O , HCN , H_2S , NO , CH_4 , C_2H_2 , O_3 , and SO_2 . Because many of these molecules are present in our original models, we summarize the additional molecules in Table B.1.

Scenario	Additional molecules included
Null	O_3 , HCN , H_2S , SO_2 , CH_4 , NO , C_2H_2
Null Dry	O_3 , HCN , H_2S , SO_2 , CH_4 , NO , C_2H_2
Cyanosulfidic	O_3 , CH_4 , NO , C_2H_2
Cyanosulfidic Dry	O_3 , CH_4 , NO , C_2H_2
Paradise	O_3 , SO_2

Table B.1: Molecules not present in the original models but added as free parameters in each validation scenario.

As the table shows, the validation test is most stringent for the *Null* and *Null Dry* cases, where seven spurious species are introduced simultaneously despite being absent

Figure B.1: Posterior distributions for molecules that are absent in at least one scenario. Green highlights indicate models where the molecule is present in the ground truth, gray indicates models where it is not.

from the underlying spectra.

In Figure B.1 we show the posteriors for all molecules that are missing from at least one model. We highlight in green the models that originally contain the molecule, and in gray the models for which the molecule was inappropriately added. This allows us to directly compare how `PyRetLIFE` retrieves molecules that are truly present with how it treats molecules that are absent.

For O_3 , CH_4 , and C_2H_2 , we see that all posteriors are upper limit (UL) types in models where the molecule is not present. For CH_4 and C_2H_2 we can directly compare the posteriors with the *Paradise* scenario, in which the molecules are indeed present and which show a very confident detection. For O_3 we see that the upper limits are all around a VMR of 10^{-8} , which is a negligible abundance that is effectively indistinguishable from zero within the sensitivity limits of the data. So we can conclude that for these three molecules our framework does not assign meaningful abundances to spurious species. The same holds for SO_2 , except that the posterior for the *Paradise* model is SL type. This suggests a tentative detection of SO_2 with a mean abundance of 10^{-8} VMR, but similar to the O_3 case this value is negligible and we can still consider this case a success. For NO , only the dry models yield upper-limit posteriors, while in the non-dry models we have unconstrained posteriors. This indicates that the

presence of water in the other models covers the NO absorption bands and prevents its detection. Due to the weak absorption of NO we can't rule out its presence in the non-dry models, and although in the dry models we have an upper limit, this is too high to be considered a proof for the absence of NO. Thus, the framework cannot rule out NO. HCN is present in all models but the *Null* and *Null Dry*, where we see an upper limit of 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} respectively. Similarly to the NO case, these are not sufficient to rule out trace amounts of HCN. However, comparing these posteriors to the other models in which HCN is indeed present, where detection is more confident as expected from its strong absorption band, suggests that a low upper limit might be enough to effectively rule out the presence of HCN. Finally, in the case of H₂S, we see that the posteriors of *Null* and *Null Dry* are effectively indistinguishable from the ones of *Cyan* and *Cyan Dry*. Considering that only in the former H₂S is absent, we can conclude that its presence can not be ruled out.

In summary, this validation exercise demonstrates that **PyRetLIFE** behaves robustly when confronted with an extended set of molecules, some of which are absent from the spectra. Across all scenarios, most spurious species are either left unconstrained or assigned negligible abundances, while molecules genuinely present in the models are consistently recovered. In the cases of NO and H₂S, the results remain inconclusive for all scenario due to their weak spectral features in the considered wavelength range. This highlights the correlation between our ability to detect a species and our ability to rule out its presence, as both rely on the presence or absence of distinct spectral features. These results confirm that the framework does not introduce false positive detections and provide confidence in its ability to reliably interpret atmospheric spectra in the presence of an expanded molecular set. Given the limited set of opacity line lists currently available, these results should be regarded as exploratory. They nonetheless provide a proof of concept and a useful guide for future, more comprehensive validation studies.

C Fixed P-T Profile Retrievals

As mentioned in Section 3.1.2, our parametrization of the P-T profile is not able to fully capture its complexity. To verify the impact of this offset we ran retrievals for all models at $S/N = 50$, keeping all parameters and priors identical, but fixing both the P-T profile and the ground pressure P_0 to their true values. Fixing P_0 together with the profile avoids re-defining the pressure grid, so the thermal structure remains identical to the input value. This allows us to test the ideal case in which our P-T profile parametrization matches perfectly the true profile.

For each model we have computed the Bayes ratio between the realistic and the ideal cases, and in all cases there is a substantial preference for the ideal model. This is expected and serves as a sanity check. We have plotted the posteriors for each parameter in Figure C.2, where we see that with a fixed P-T profile there is, on average, an improvement in the *Null*, *Null Dry*, and *Cyan Dry* models, while the opposite holds for the *Cyan* and *Paradise* scenarios. Before discussing the individual parameters, we notice a systematic broadening of several posteriors, which can be attributed to the reduced flexibility of the model once the thermal structure is fixed. In the retrievals with free P-T profile, uncertainties in the temperature gradient can partially compensate for mismatches in other parameters, thereby producing artificially tight posteriors. Once the P-T is fixed this freedom is lost, and the posteriors better reflect the true degeneracies among parameters.

The radius is consistently better constrained when the P-T profile is fixed. This follows from the fact that the observed flux level scales with the emitting area and the temperature of the radiating layers (the photosphere). In the free P-T case, part of the amplitude of the spectrum can be adjusted through changes in temperature¹, which weakens the constraint on R_{pl} . Once the thermal structure is fixed this degeneracy is removed and the radius becomes more tightly determined in all models.

For the planetary mass we see a clear difference in the way the dry and non-dry models respond to fixing the P-T structure. In the non-dry cases the mass posterior tightens significantly, while in the dry models it instead broadens. This indicates that the water profile plays a central role in shaping the retrieval performance, as it couples strongly to the P-T structure as discussed in Section 2.3.1. Whether the mass posterior tightens or broadens with a fixed P-T profile depends on how well the spectrum can still anchor the pressure scale. This is because how pressure changes with height depends on the strength of gravity, which in turn informs us about the mass. In the non-dry cases this anchoring is strong, thanks to vertically structured H_2O : water has strong bands spanning multiple wavelengths, meaning that they are emitted at different pressures². When its abundance varies with altitude and with a fixed P-T profile, these bands provide cues about the pressures. With a retrieved P-T profile, similar contrasts could

¹For thermal emission, the flux scales approximately as $F_\lambda \propto R_{\text{pl}}^2 B_\lambda(T_{\text{ph}})$, where B_λ is the Planck function at the photospheric temperature T_{ph} . Variations in T can therefore mimic changes in R_{pl} and weaken its constraint.

²The photosphere is at optical depth $\tau_\lambda \approx 1$, and since the optical depth varies with wavelength, the different bands of water are emitted in different atmospheric layers with different pressures.

Figure C.1: Retrieved H_2O profiles for the *Null*, *Cyan* and *Paradise* models at $S/N = 50$ with P - T profile and P_0 fixed to their true values. The shaded bands represent the 90 %, 70 %, 50 % and 30 % credible intervals while the black line represents the true profile.

instead be reproduced by adjusting the temperature gradient, introducing degeneracies that weaken the mass constraint. It’s important to point out that in our case the water profile is severely underestimated as shown in Figure C.1. This however, does not invalidate our analysis: the variability of H_2O still explains the tightening of the posterior, while the offset from the true profile propagates into the mass, explaining its underestimation. In the dry cases H_2O is constant with altitude, so the different bands provide fewer additional cues. This means that fixing the P - T structure only removes information encoded in the temperature gradient without adding new constraints on the pressure scale. As a result, the information on M_{pl} decrease and the posterior broadens.

For the molecular abundances we notice that in the *Cyan* and *Paradise* scenarios, where the water profile varies with pressure, the retrieval performance is degraded when the P - T and P_0 are fixed. In these cases, as seen in Figure C.1, the fixed thermal structure is inconsistent with the retrieved water profile, which is heavily underestimated. This leads not only to broader posteriors but also to systematic shifts of the medians. While the first effect is caused by the lack of flexibility that a free P - T structure would provide, the latter is a consequence of the poorly retrieved water profile: the medians shift systematically because the retrieval is forced to accommodate an underestimated water content. We do not see this poor retrieval performance in the *Null Dry* and *Cyan Dry* models, where the retrieved water abundance aligns very well with the true value. This confirms that H_2O is the key driver of the worsening posteriors. In the *Null* model we would expect behaviors similar to the other non-dry models, but due to its limited number of parameters we observe only an improvement in the CO_2 constraint. This seems to diverge from the *Cyan* and *Paradise* models behavior, where the CO_2 estimation worsens, but it is in fact in line with the expected behavior of a decrease in the CO_2 posterior median, which occurs in all scenarios. The reason is that a decrease in overall water content removes a powerful absorber at all wavelengths, making the continuum stronger and all other absorption features appear deeper.

Figure C.2: Posterior distributions of all retrieved molecules for all models at $S/N = 50$. Solid lines represent the free P - T retrievals, while dashed lines represent the ideal case with P - T profile and P_0 fixed to their true values. Gray bands indicate the ± 0.5 dex regions, while the light-blue band in the radius posterior marks the ± 0.05 dex region. The black line within each band denotes the true value.

If the temperature cannot be adjusted, the retrieval reduces the abundances of other strong absorbers to avoid overestimating their band depths. This effect is particularly visible for CO₂ because of its large abundance and strong absorption bands, but the same compensating mechanism may also influence other molecules.

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich

Declaration of originality

The signed declaration of originality is a component of every written paper or thesis authored during the course of studies. **In consultation with the supervisor**, one of the following two options must be selected:

- I hereby declare that I authored the work in question independently, i.e. that no one helped me to author it. Suggestions from the supervisor regarding language and content are excepted. I used no generative artificial intelligence technologies¹.
- I hereby declare that I authored the work in question independently. In doing so I only used the authorised aids, which included suggestions from the supervisor regarding language and content and generative artificial intelligence technologies. The use of the latter and the respective source declarations proceeded in consultation with the supervisor.

Title of paper or thesis:

DETECTION OF PREBIOSIGNATURE MOLECULES IN TEMPERATE
EXOPLANETARY ATMOSPHERES WITH LIFE

Authored by:

If the work was compiled in a group, the names of all authors are required.

Last name(s):

Bottomi

First name(s):

Jacopo

With my signature I confirm the following:

- I have adhered to the rules set out in the [Citation Guidelines](#).
- I have documented all methods, data and processes truthfully and fully.
- I have mentioned all persons who were significant facilitators of the work.

I am aware that the work may be screened electronically for originality.

Place, date

Zürich, 06.10.2025

Signature(s)

J. Bottomi

If the work was compiled in a group, the names of all authors are required. Through their signatures they vouch jointly for the entire content of the written work.

¹ For further information please consult the ETH Zurich websites, e.g. <https://ethz.ch/en/the-eth-zurich/education/ai-in-education.html> and <https://library.ethz.ch/en/researching-and-publishing/scientific-writing-at-eth-zurich.html> (subject to change).